

D1.3

Report on Collection of existing contents, tools and good practices – 1st version

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NAME	ORGANISATION
LOUIS FERRINI	FVA
LILY TEITELBAUM	BIOCOM

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1. Executive Summary

This report provides the description of the adopted methodologies and the results at month 8 of Task 1.2 - Collection of contents, tools, databases, platforms and good practices.

The resulting collection shows the available contents and materials for the awareness-raising, communication, and education activities, addressing various stakeholders in the European Bioeconomy.

The collected tools can be exploited and maximised through the other tasks of the WP1, i.e. the creation of the awareness, communication, and education toolkits (T1.3) and the Transition2BIO resources Library (T1.4). The Library will gather and deliver the tools to the public, while selected tools will be used for the production of the toolkits.

Results on the current collection are summarised in the document, providing some information on the tools. The most remarkable finding is the interest of the main actors developing contents and tools predominantly in the MULTIPLIERS and the SUPPORTIVE ENVIRONMENT, as most of the tools addressed this target group. It is also evident the need to pay more attention to the communication needs of their audiences and stakeholders in relation to the formats in which the information is channelled to them, such as in terms of available languages and formats.

A plan for the future development of the collection is outlined in this deliverable, pointing out methodologies to enrich the collection with additional tools and information. A better description and characterisation of the tools will provide insights for the exploitation of the tools and recommendations for their use.

2. Introduction and objective

The transition towards a sustainable bioeconomy can lead to positive environmental and socio-economic impacts. Making people aware of this potential and providing the needed skills in the bioeconomy are key challenges for change (European Commission, 2018).

The Transition2BIO project will build upon the most relevant communication and education EU-funded projects and initiatives to contribute to the implementation of the Updated 2018 EU Bioeconomy Strategy (European Commission, 2018), and promote the transition towards a more sustainable production, consumption, and lifestyle by implementing an integrated package of activities addressing a wide range of target stakeholders, namely: DEMAND SIDE (consumers, citizens, B2B, public procurers, etc.); SUPPLY SIDE (primary production, production industries, biorefineries, etc.); MULTIPLIERS and SUPPORTIVE ENVIRONMENT (citizens' organisations, NGOs and other associations, brands, retailers, teachers, EU-funded projects and initiatives, influencers, media, policy makers, regional authorities, initiatives, networks, clusters, etc.).

Among the strategic objectives of the project, Transition2BIO aims to valorise and exploit sectoral communication tools and activities developed at national, regional, and local level by EU-funded bioeconomy projects and other relevant initiatives (SO1). This is also the general objective of the WP1 for the creation of the awareness-raising, communication, and education toolkits.

The target beneficiaries' needs, interests and motivations for these activities are pointed out in the Deliverable 1.1 - Conceptual framework of the awareness, communication and education toolkits – 1st version.

In particular, the task 1.2 sets out to collect and analyse, exploit and maximize the available awareness, communication and education materials and tools (i.e. presentations, articles, publications, policy briefs, case studies, good practices, fact sheets, infographics, games, quizzes, videos, info educational and training materials), as well as the existing knowledge about the bioeconomy at large and the environmental and socio-economic benefits of all bioeconomy areas, from at least 100 different sources. In the context of this report, the term source means the project or initiative from which a tool was collected.

The collected materials will be used in the project for the production of the toolkits (T1.3), and delivered in a transparent, readily available, user-friendly, and visual-attractive way through the Transition2BIO resources Library (T1.4).

This deliverable D1.3 reports the methodology (Section 3) and results (Section 4) of the collection (T1.2), as well as its limitations, and possible interpretations and implications (Section 5 *Discussion*). The conclusions are outlined in the Section 6.

In section 5, the intents for the future development of the T1.2 are also outlined.

The integral collection of the materials is provided in the Annex section.

3. Methodology

Relying on previous experiences of the Transition2BIO consortium, the project envisaged selecting the sources for the collection of materials from the following types of EU-funded projects and initiatives:

- EU funded projects in bioeconomy awareness and communication (e.g., BLOWAYS, BioSTEP, BioCannDo, BIOVOICES, BIOBRIDGES, BLOOM, LIFT) in different programmes (H2020, Interreg, Erasmus+, etc.).
- Other relevant EU-funded projects dealing with the Bioeconomy at large in different programmes (H2020, Interreg, Erasmus+, etc.).
- European Commission (EC)'s initiatives and platforms (e.g., Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy (JRC), European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform, European Rural Development Network, FIT4FOOD2030, etc.).

This work should have built upon:

- LIFT's European Bioeconomy Library¹, managed by FVA and LOBA, which collects and delivers in a structured way the main outcomes of many bioeconomy projects (mainly CSAs or CSA-like in H2020, Interreg, Erasmus+ and other programmes).
- Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy, managed by JRC, mainly targeting policymakers.
- The exploitable awareness and communication assets from BIOVOICES, BLOOM, BLOWAYS, BioSTEP, Biobridges, LIFT, SHERPA, BE-Rural, NEXTFOOD, BoostEdu, Transition to Green Economy, XPRESS, European Bioeconomy University, where partners are involved.

To ensure the achievement of the target of at least 100 EU-funded bioeconomy projects, networks and initiatives, the risk-mitigation measures of the project proposed that Transition2BIO analysis should have been based, as a starting point, on the LIFT's European Bioeconomy Library. Additionally, initiatives like the European Bioeconomy Network (EuBioNet) and the European Bioeconomy University (EBU) have been analysed.

Following these indications, the sources were identified among the projects collected by the European Bioeconomy Library, the European Bioeconomy Network's projects and initiatives partners, the European Bioeconomy University's projects, and from the European Commission's initiatives, like the Joint Research Centre and Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy.

¹ <https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu>

From each source, the available tools were identified and collected in a database shared with the project's consortium.

Resources not related to awareness-raising, communication, and education activities in the European Bioeconomy were excluded from the collection. Materials that were not accessible and freely available were excluded as well. Alternatively, tools that required a free registration on a web platform were considered.

Contents related only to the dissemination and communication of the sources' scopes and methodologies were not collected.

The year of publication and the language of the tools were not chosen as eligibility criteria for the collection, not setting time or linguistic limitations.

For each tool, the following descriptors were identified and pointed out in the database:

- Language(s)
- Title of the tool
- Content type
- Target group
- Source
- Year of publication
- Link to the tool

The classification of the tools for the “content type” descriptor followed the content type categories of the LIFT European Bioeconomy Library.

4. Results

A total of 926 tools were collected from 97 different sources (Table 1). The tools target mainly (and by large) MULTIPLIERS and SUPPORTIVE ENVIRONMENT (746 tools), while less attention is given to the DEMAND SIDE (64) and SUPPLY SIDE (98) (Fig. 1).

Table 1. List of the sources.

No.	Source	Type of source	No. of materials collected from the source
1	ABBEE	Erasmus+ project	1
2	Agrimax	H2020 project	27
3	AllThings.Bio	H2020 project	20
4	AlpBioEco	Interreg project	41
5	Askfood	Erasmus+ project	6
6	BalticBiomass4Value	Interreg project	16
7	Be-Rural	H2020 project	107
8	Becoteps	FP7 project	1
9	Berst	FP7 project	11
10	Bio Base NWE	Interreg project	7
11	Bio-Art Gallery	Gallery	1
12	Bio4Eco	Interreg project	28
13	Bio4Products	H2020 project	18
14	BioBase4SME	Interreg project	12
15	Biobridges	H2020 project	20
16	BioCannDo	H2020 project	15
17	BIOEASTSUP	H2020 project	3
18	Bioecon	Erasmus+ project	3
19	BIOES GAME	Game	1
20	Biolinx	H2020 project	3
21	Biomonitor	H2020 project	14
22	Bioøkonomi	Magazine	4
23	BIOPEN	H2020 project	1
24	BIOPROM	FP7 project	2
25	BIOREG	H2020 project	14
26	BIOREGIO	Interreg project	8
27	Biorescue	H2020 project	6
28	BioSTEP	H2020 project	14
29	BIOSWITCH	H2020 project	10
30	BIOVOICES	H2020 project	50
31	BIOWAYS	H2020 project	23

32	BISO	FP7 project	2
33	BLOOM	H2020 project	28
34	Campus de Métiers et de Qualifications d'excellence BioEco Academy	Initiative	8
35	CommBeBiz	H2020 project	25
36	CommFABNet	FP7 project	2
37	CONSOLE	H2020 project	1
38	DanuBioValNet	Interreg project	4
39	European Bioeconomy University (EBU)	Initiative	1
40	EMBRACED	H2020 project	3
41	Enabling	H2020 project	3
42	ERIFORE	H2020 project	9
43	EU Research & Innovation	EC Directorate-General	2
44	EU Science & Innovation	EC Directorate-General	2
45	EUFRUIT	H2020 project	1
46	European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform	Initiative	6
47	European Network for Rural Development	Initiative	11
48	FASTER	H2020 project	3
49	Fertimanure	H2020 project	1
50	Fields	Erasmus+ project	3
51	Fit4Food2030	H2020 project	10
52	Food-STA	Erasmus+ project	6
53	GBO	Interreg project	3
54	Glaukos	H2020 project	1
55	GoDanuBio	Interreg	2
56	Greenchemistry Lombardia	Initiative	1
57	GreenProtein	H2020 project	1
58	ICT-BIOCHAIN	H2020 project	6
59	InnProBio	H2020 project	8
60	Interreg Europe	Initiative	1
61	Interreg MED Green Growth	Initiative	4
62	Intrinsic	Erasmus+ project	2
63	ISAAC	H2020 project	8
64	Isabel	H2020 project	3
65	Joint Research Centre (JRC)	EC service	5
66	KBBPPS	FP7 project	5
67	Key steps to establishing a Digital Innovation Hub	Initiative	1
68	Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy	EC initiative	16
69	LEAP4FNSSA	H2020 project	2
70	Lifecab	LIFE project	1
71	LIFT	H2020 project	12
72	Magic	H2020 project	4
73	MPowerBio	H2020 project	1

74	NextFOOD	H2020 project	22
75	Open-Bio	FP7 project	9
76	Pilots4U	H2020 project	4
77	POWER4BIO	H2020 project	14
78	ProBIO	H2020 project	3
79	RD12CluB	Interreg project	9
80	Refresh	H2020 project	13
81	ReMIX	H2020 project	8
82	RoadToBio	H2020 project	4
83	Rubizmo	H2020 project	9
84	S2Biom	FP7 project	61
85	SAT-BBE	FP7 project	4
86	SCALIBUR	H2020 project	4
87	SHERPA	H2020 project	10
88	Smartchain	H2020 project	1
89	SmarPilots	Interreg project	2
90	STAR-PROBIO	H2020 project	17
91	STAR4BBI	H2020 project	6
92	SuperBIO	H2020 project	1
93	Tradeit	FP7 project	2
94	Transition2BIO	H2020 project	2
95	Urbiofuture	H2020 project	13
96	Valuewaste	H2020 project	2
97	Waystup	H2020 project	1

Figure 1. Distribution of tools by target groups.

The tools were classified as ‘Multiple target groups’ (19 tools) when it was not possible to identify only a single type of target group for them. This does not imply that other tools may

not have been targeted or not be appropriate to more than one target groups. Even for the 'Multiple target groups' tools, the addressed target groups have been indicated. In the Annex, it is possible to see specifically the target groups identified for each tool.

Most of the collected tools are in English (Fig. 2), but the tools available in other languages show a large linguistic diversity including a total of 23 languages: Bulgarian (19 tools), Chinese (1), Danish (1), Dutch (8), Estonian (1), German (20), Greek (3), English (770), Finnish (4), French (10), Hungarian (1), Italian (13), Latvian (15), Lithuanian (1), Macedonian (17), Norwegian (4), Polish (20), Portuguese (3), Romanian (18), Slovak (1), Slovenian (6), Spanish (8), Swedish (2).

Figure 2. Number of tools for each language.

The tools were also classified according to the type of content. The "Content type" categories of the European Bioeconomy Library were used²: Article, Case Study, Database or repository, Fact Sheet³, Games, Good practice, Infographics³, Multimedia/video, Platform, Policy Brief,

² "Network/cluster/initiative" category was not considered.

³ "Fact Sheet" and "Infographics" were considered as two different categories, unlike what has been done in the European Bioeconomy Library.

Presentation, Project deliverable, Project progress/final report, Publication, Recommendation, Training material, Other.

Figure 3. Number of tools for each content type.

Project deliverable (223 tools) and Presentation (131) are the most frequent content types (Fig. 3), while Article (9), Infographics (7), and Project progress/final report (3) are the less frequent ones.

5. Discussion

5.1 Main outcomes

The analysis of the collected tools mainly suggests unbalanced attention of the main actors developing contents and tools in the European Bioeconomy for those who may amplify their messages, instead of focusing on their end targets. These targets may be justified by the early stage of development of the sector; however, this may need attention and, potentially, a change of strategy for the future.

The frequencies of the content types are consistent with this view, since the ‘more immediate to understand’ tools (like, for example, the Infographics and Games) are less frequent than those for bioeconomy experts, like the Project deliverables and Publications.

English predominance in the collection could be a possible limit to the usability of the tools, as even some multipliers usually enjoy materials in their native languages (DESIRE, 2013). However, the presence of tools in many other languages is interesting, showing possible concern of these actors towards the practical needs of the stakeholders and stake in the geographical spread of their materials.

The majority of the tools lacks the indication of the year of publication (data not shown). This descriptor will be analysed more accurately in the next steps of the collection (section 5.3). On the other hand, it shows an interesting aspect to be addressed by the contents’ creators, as their audiences may need to know and evaluate the currentness of a document (The University of Akron, 2021).

5.2 Limitations

This collection and the analysis of available awareness-raising, communication, and education tools in the European Bioeconomy have some limitations for the understanding of the extent of these materials and for the identification of the elements characterising the tools. Indeed, further work is needed to enlarge our research and evaluate the use of the tools.

At this stage, the research of the available tools considered mainly EU-funded projects and initiatives, and only a limited number of these have been taken into account. Materials and sources from many other institutions and stakeholders were not collected, while they could provide interesting angles and examples in the landscape of the information exchange in the European Bioeconomy.

Furthermore, for the tools, only some descriptors and the related information were considered and collected. Other descriptors and information will be needed to characterise and

understand at a deeper level the tools, also in order to provide usability- and usefulness-oriented recommendations for the use and exploitation of them.

The coverage of all bioeconomy sectors, aimed by the project, by the available tools in the European Bioeconomy have to be estimated and understood.

A detailed description on how to further develop the collection, also addressing these limitations and providing future directions for this research, has been set out in section 5.3.

5.3 Future development of the collection

This section shows the next steps for T1.2.

Firstly, it is planned to complete the collection with the methodologies outlined in section 3, as well as to enrich the collection through the suggestion of further relevant sources and materials by the consortium partners.

Other additional tools and sources will be added also through searches in specific repositories. The repositories and the keywords for the searches still have to be identified.

The tools may come from any type of source, while their eligibility criteria will be the same as those described in section 3.

Considering the number of sources from which the materials have been already collected, it is expected to exceed the Mile Stone 1 - Collection of contents, tools, databases, platforms and good practices from at least 100 different sources.

The enriched collection will include a general characterization of the tools (with the same type of information collected for the current collection).

In the updated collection, for each tool, will be also pointed out the following additional descriptors:

- Sub-target group
- Geographical focus
- Year of publication
- Bioeconomy sector(s) focus

Afterwards, a shorter list of the tools will be selected, including only the content types we do assume to be the most interactive, or user-friendly, or worthwhile for the target groups' needs:

- Case study
- Factsheet
- Games

- Good practice
- Infographics
- Policy brief
- Training material
- Video

The selected tools will be evaluated by the consortium partners and by the members of the Advisory Board with the following criteria:

- The level of responding to the questions outlined for the objectives of the Toolkits in the Deliverable 1.1 - Conceptual framework of the awareness, communication and education toolkits – 1st version
 - For tools targeting the DEMAND SIDE: *What is bioeconomy? What are the bioeconomy areas? What are the benefits and impacts for the society, the environment and the economy? What is the contribution of the demand side in driving the transition towards a more sustainable consumption and lifestyle?*
 - For tools targeting the SUPPLY SIDE: *What is bioeconomy? What are the bioeconomy areas? What are the opportunities for my sector? What are promising regional business models? How can I valorise my residues? What is the contribution of the supply side in driving the transition towards a more sustainable production? What are possible financial opportunities for bioeconomy sectors?*
 - For tools targeting the MULTIPLIERS and the SUPPORTIVE ENVIRONMENT: *How to communicate and support bioeconomy?*
- The comprehensibility of the language (textual and visual)
- The ease of use

These steps will provide a thorough characterisation of the selected tools and recommendations on how to foster the exploitation of the available and most useful tools for awareness-raising, communication, and education activities in the European Bioeconomy.

The rationale of this section was partly inspired by POWER4BIO (2019).

6. Conclusions

This collection provides us with a basic but informative picture of the materials disseminated in the European Bioeconomy regarding awareness-raising, communication, and education activities.

From the analysis of these tools, it is advisable for EU-funded projects and initiatives to pay greater attention to the communication needs of their audiences. They should consider and address their linguistic needs and design easily accessible and understandable dissemination materials on their data, results, and evidence.

The future enrichment of the collection with additional tools and descriptors, following the steps outlined in section 5.3, will allow a deeper understanding of the extent of the information exchange materials in the European Bioeconomy. At the same time, it will make us comprehend usability- and usefulness-related information about the tools.

The results of the future development of the collection will be discussed in the D1.4 – Report on Collection of existing contents, tools and good practices – update on month 23.

The collection will be publicly delivered in a transparent, readily available, user-friendly, and visual-attractive way through the Transition2BIO resources Library (T1.4).

A selection of the collected tools will be used in the project for the production of the toolkits (T1.3), as well as for other activities.

7. References

DESIRE. (2013). *REACH OUT Toolkit*. Retrieved from DESIRE: <http://desire.eun.org/toolkit>

European Commission. (2018). *A sustainable bioeconomy for Europe - Strengthening the connection between economy, society and the environment: Updated Bioeconomy Strategy*.

POWER4BIO. (2019). *Recommendations for the use of existing tools when developing regional bioeconomy strategies Deliverable 2.3*. Retrieved from POWER4BIO: https://power4bio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/POWER4BIO_D2.3_Tool_inventory_190531_FV.pdf

The University of Akron, University Libraries, Instructional Services. (2021). *Evaluate Your Sources (Wayne College): Evaluating for Currency*. Retrieved from Evaluate Your Sources (Wayne College): Evaluating for Currency: https://libguides.uakron.edu/wayne_CRAAP/currency

8. Annex

Table 2. Collection of tools.

Language	Title of the tool	Content type	Target group	Source	Link
EN	ABBEE - Our courses	Database or repository	Demand	ABBEE	https://www.abee.eu/
EN	Agrimax D1.1 State-of-the-art review of bio-waste derived compounds	Project deliverable	Supply	Agrimax	https://agromax.iris.cat/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/Agrimax-D1.1-State-of-the-art-review-of-bio-waste-derived-compounds.pdf
EN	Agrimax D1.2 Mapping of AFPW and their characteristics	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Agrimax	https://agromax.iris.cat/wp-content/uploads/2017/11/AGRIMAX-D.1.2_Mapping-of-AFPW-and-their-characteristics.pdf
EN	Agrimax D7.4 Standard and legislative aspects	Project deliverable	Supply	Agrimax	https://agromax.iris.cat/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/Agrimax-D7.6-Standard-and-legislative-aspects.pdf
EN	Agrimax D8.5 Proceedings on the Stakeholder Workshop on AFPW sustainable value chains	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Agrimax	https://agromax.iris.cat/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/AgriMAX-Stakeholder-Workshop-Proceedings_final.pdf
EN	AF Biomass Limited in East Anglia, UK	Case study	Supply	Agrimax	https://agromax.iris.cat/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/AF-Biomass-Limited-in-East-Anglia-UK.pdf
EN	Granville Ecopark in Tyrone, Northern Ireland (UK)	Case study	Supply	Agrimax	https://agromax.iris.cat/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/Granville-Ecopark-in-Tyrone-Northern-Ireland-UK.pdf
EN	Soldebre in Catalonia, Spain	Case study	Supply	Agrimax	https://agromax.iris.cat/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/Soldebre-in-Catalonia-Spain.pdf
EN	Steeper Energy and Silva Green Fuel in Hurum, Norway	Case study	Supply	Agrimax	https://agromax.iris.cat/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/Steeper-Energy-and-Silva-Green-Fuel-in-Hurum-Norway.pdf
EN	Wilson Bio-Chemical in Yorkshire, UK	Case study	Supply	Agrimax	https://agromax.iris.cat/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/Wilson-Bio-Chemical-in-Yorkshire-UK.pdf
EN	Using cereal waste to develop novel products for the food, packaging and agricultural sector	Fact Sheet	Supply, Multiplier	Agrimax	https://agromax.iris.cat/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/Using-cereal-waste-to-develop-novel-products-for-the-food-packaging-and-agricultural-sector-1.pdf
EN	Using olive residues to develop novel products for the food and packaging sectors	Fact Sheet	Supply, Multiplier	Agrimax	https://agromax.iris.cat/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/Using-olive-residues-to-develop-novel-products-for-the-food-and-packaging-sectors.pdf
EN	Using potato waste to develop novel agricultural films and pots	Fact Sheet	Supply, Multiplier	Agrimax	https://agromax.iris.cat/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/Using-potato-waste-to-develop-novel-agricultural-films-and-pots.pdf
EN	Using tomato waste to make novel products for the food and packaging sectors: cutin and lycopene	Fact Sheet	Supply, Multiplier	Agrimax	https://agromax.iris.cat/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/Using-tomato-waste-to-make-novel-products-for-the-food-and-packaging-sectors-cutin-and-lycopene.pdf
EN	Using tomato waste to make agricultural fertilisers	Fact Sheet	Supply, Multiplier	Agrimax	https://agromax.iris.cat/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/Using-tomato-waste-to-make-agricultural-fertilisers.pdf
EN	Video: Agrimax – creating a greener, more sustainable Europe	Video	Multiplier	Agrimax	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=b4lMniY6qvU
EN	Video: Agrimax – commissioning the Italian Pilot Plant (biorefinery)	Video	Multiplier	Agrimax	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Ci6TAei4l6I&t=2s
EN	Video: a flexible, multi feedstock Pilot Plant in Italy	Video	Multiplier	Agrimax	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hNfY9KOZAjk
EN	Video: commissioning the Italian Pilot Plant	Video	Multiplier	Agrimax	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Ci6TAei4l6I
EN	Video: extracting cutin from tomato waste	Video	Multiplier	Agrimax	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mf9KZA630IQ&t=83s
EN	Video: turning tomato waste into hydrocompost	Video	Multiplier	Agrimax	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-8qqa0C6CSk

EN	Video: turning wheat bran waste into biopolymers	Video	Multiplier	AgriMax	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1T_m6wV38wE
EN	Video: turning wheat bran waste into ferulic acid	Video	Multiplier	AgriMax	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OCVhJO5VH38
EN	Video: Developing innovative products from potato waste for the agricultural industry	Video	Multiplier	AgriMax	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Q40OmZT1dw
EN	Video: Turning cereals into advanced cellulose	Video	Multiplier	AgriMax	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BrNW64aHy8s
EN	Video: Turning olive waste into polyphenols and protein enrichment	Video	Multiplier	AgriMax	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=s3GrNbmtVr8
EN	Video: Assessment of impact on soils	Video	Multiplier	AgriMax	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gipKkrbs_ig
EN	Video: Environmental and economic sustainability assessment	Video	Multiplier	AgriMax	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YLVm1QSQ1ul
EN	The bioeconomy: a brief introduction	Publication	Demand	AllThings.Bio	https://www.allthings.bio/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/Bioeconomy_EN_2104.pdf
EN	Sustainable fashion	Fact Sheet	Demand	AllThings.Bio	https://www.allthings.bio/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/Fashion_EN_2104.pdf
EN	Food Packaging	Fact Sheet	Demand	AllThings.Bio	https://www.allthings.bio/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/FoodPackaging_EN_2104.pdf
EN	Jobs and Careers in the bioeconomy	Fact Sheet	Demand, Supply, Multiplier	AllThings.Bio	https://www.allthings.bio/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/JobsCareers_EN_2104.pdf
EN	Kids & Schools	Fact Sheet	Multiplier	AllThings.Bio	https://www.allthings.bio/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/KidsSchools_EN_2104-1.pdf
EN	Quiz #4 – Bio-based or biodegradable: that is the question!	Games	Demand	AllThings.Bio	https://www.allthings.bio/quiz/quiz-4-bio-based-or-biodegradable-that-is-the-question/
EN	Quiz#5 – Bio-based food packaging	Games	Demand	AllThings.Bio	https://www.allthings.bio/quiz/quiz5-bio-based-food-packaging/
EN	Quiz #3 – Find out how bio-based insulation can keep you warm this winter	Games	Demand	AllThings.Bio	https://www.allthings.bio/quiz/quiz-3-bio-based-insulation-materials-find-out-how-bio-based-insulation-can-keep-you-warm-this-winter/
EN	Facts or Myth „Biodegradability“	Article	Demand	AllThings.Bio	https://www.allthings.bio/fact-or-myth/facts-or-myth-biodegradability/
EN	Quiz 2 – Gear up and test your knowledge on biofuels!	Games	Demand	AllThings.Bio	https://www.allthings.bio/quiz/quiz-2-gear-up-and-test-your-knowledge-on-biofuels/
EN	Quiz #1 – Are you ready for the bioeconomy?	Games	Demand	AllThings.Bio	https://www.allthings.bio/quiz/are-you-ready-for-the-bioeconomy/
EN	Bio-based Soap	Video	Demand	AllThings.Bio	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=a2G_Mu1eN4Y
EN	Bio-based Straws	Video	Demand	AllThings.Bio	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HUT3XO--tjg
EN	Bio-based plates	Video	Demand	AllThings.Bio	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SR-blqNlCP4
EN	Bio-based toy	Video	Demand	AllThings.Bio	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KQCUsTqn4MA
EN	Bio-based home cleaning products	Video	Demand	AllThings.Bio	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ldi75qioGUw
EN	Durable Bio-based coffee mug	Video	Demand	AllThings.Bio	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7QXtsV7dJIE
EN	Bio-based t-shirt	Video	Demand	AllThings.Bio	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RhWVzHy82tU
EN	Bio-based lipstick	Video	Demand	AllThings.Bio	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=K52E6Z4a0R5
EN	AllThings.Bio - Game changer for the bio-based economy	Video	Multiplier	AllThings.Bio	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mCkQYzvsKY&t=3s
EN	Recipes from walnut press cake	Other	Demand	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioeco/publications/promotional-activities/recipes_walnut-press-cake_kern-illustrated.pdf
EN	Recipes from apple pomace flour	Other	Demand	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/directuploads/bricks/brick-downloadlist/apple-pomace-flour-recipes.pdf
EN	Crazy About Apples: Recipes, ideas, challenges, facts, anecdotes	Other	Demand	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioeco/publications/promotional-activities/publication-crazy-about-apples-of-selected-quality.pdf
DE	Master-Thesis Entwicklung von zukunftsfähigen Geschäftsmodellen für bioökonomische Innovationen im Alpenraum am Beispiel der Wertschöpfungskette Walnüsse im Rahmen des Projektes AlpBioEco	Publication	Multiplier	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioeco/projects-results/collab-universities/masterthesis_veronika_anonymisiert.pdf
EN	Comparing selected bioeconomy strategies of European countries within the frame of the AlpBioEco project	Publication	Multiplier	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioeco/projects-results/collab-universities/2020-july-comparing-selected-bioeconomy-strategies.pdf
EN	AlpBioEco report - results and replicable roadmap	Project deliverable	Supply	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioeco/projects-results/alpbioeco_results-and-replicable-roadmap.pdf

EN	AlpBioEco replicable roadmap, practical guide, June 2020 (English)	Project deliverable	Supply	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioeco/projects-results/roadmap_kern-final_03-07-20_final.pdf
EN	AlpBioEco replicable roadmap (English)	Project deliverable	Supply	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioeco/projects-results/hsa-alpbioeco-roadmap-gb-ly_01.pdf
DE	AlpBioEco replicable roadmap (German)	Project deliverable	Supply	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioeco/projects-results/hsa-alpbioeco-roadmap-de-ly_02.pdf
IT	AlpBioEco replicable roadmap (Italian)	Project deliverable	Supply	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioeco/projects-results/hsa-alpbioeco-roadmap-it-ly_03.pdf
FR	AlpBioEco replicable roadmap (French)	Project deliverable	Supply	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioeco/projects-results/hsa-alpbioeco-roadmap-fr-ly_03.pdf
SL	AlpBioEco replicable roadmap (Slovenian)	Project deliverable	Supply	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioeco/projects-results/hsa-alpbioeco-roadmap-sl-ly_04.pdf
EN	Processing and marketing recommendations - Envipark	Recommendation	Multiplier	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioeco/projects-results/processing-and-marketing-recommendations---envipark.pdf
EN	Business models (Deliverable 2-1)	Project deliverable	Supply	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioeco/projects-results/wp2/01_alpbioeco_wp2_d2-1-v4.pdf
EN	Good and bad practices (Deliverable 2-2)	Good practice	Supply	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioeco/projects-results/wp2/02_alpbioeco_wp2_d2-2-v3.pdf
EN	Success factors (Deliverable 2-3)	Project deliverable	Multiplier	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioeco/projects-results/wp2/03_alpbioeco_wp2_d2-3-v4.pdf
EN	Missing linkages (Deliverable 2-4)	Project deliverable	Multiplier	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioeco/projects-results/wp2/04_alpbioeco_wp2_d2-4-v3.pdf
EN	AlpBioEco Best Practice Brochure - English	Good practice	Supply	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioeco/projects-results/wp3/hsa-alpbioeco-best-practice-brochure-final-lowres.pdf
SL	AlpBioEco Best Practice Brochure - Slovenian	Good practice	Supply	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioeco/projects-results/wp3/alpbioeco-best-practice-brochure---slovenian.pdf
EN	Disposable tableware and biodegradable packaging - Upper Austria - Austria (English)	Project deliverable	Multiplier	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioeco/projects-results/rigs/alpbioeco_wp-t4_rig_apple_disposable-tableware-and-biodegradable-packaging_bizup_engl_v1.pdf
DE	Disposable tableware and biodegradable packaging - Upper Austria - Austria (German)	Project deliverable	Multiplier	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioeco/projects-results/rigs/alpbioeco_wp-t4_rig_appel_einweggeschirr-und-biol-abbaubare-verpackungen_bizup_dt_v1.pdf
IT	Disposable tableware and biodegradable packaging - Autonomous Province Bozen/Bolzano - Italy (English)	Project deliverable	Multiplier	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioeco/projects-results/rigs/alpbioeco_wp-t4_rig_noi-ag_disposable-tableware-and-biodegradable-packaging_engl_v1.pdf
DE	Disposable tableware and biodegradable packaging - Autonomous Province Bozen/Bolzano - Italy (German)	Project deliverable	Multiplier	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioeco/projects-results/rigs/alpbioeco_wp-t4_rig_noi-ag_einweggeschirr-und-biologisch-abbaubare-verpackungen_v1.pdf
EN	Apple flour - Piedmont Region - Italy (English)	Project deliverable	Multiplier	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioeco/projects-results/rigs/alpbioeco_wp-t4_rig_apple_piedmont-region_envipark_eng_v1.pdf
IT	Apple flour - Piedmont Region - Italy (Italian)	Project deliverable	Multiplier	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioeco/projects-results/rigs/alpbioeco_wp-t4_rig_apple_piedmont-region_envipark_ita_v1.pdf
EN	Walnut Flips - Auvergne Rhône Alps - France (English)	Project deliverable	Multiplier	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioeco/projects-results/rigs/alpbioeco_rig_france_region-aura_walnut-flips_english_v1.pdf
FR	Walnut Flips - Auvergne Rhône Alps - France (French)	Project deliverable	Multiplier	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioeco/projects-results/rigs/alpbioeco_rig_france_region-aura_walnut-flips_french_v1.pdf
EN	Walnut Flips - Tübingen/Oberschwaben - Germany (English)	Recommendation	Multiplier	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioeco/projects-results/rigs/alpbioeco_wp-t4_regional-implementation-guidelines_walnut_flips_bund_english.pdf
DE	Walnut Flips - Tübingen/Oberschwaben - Germany (German)	Recommendation	Multiplier	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioeco/projects-results/rigs/alpbioeco_wp-t4_regional-implementation-guidelines_walnut_flips_bund_deutsch.pdf
DE	Walnut Spreads- Tübingen/Oberschwaben - Germany (German)	Recommendation	Multiplier	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioeco/projects-results/rigs/alpbioeco_wp-t4_template-regional-implementation-guidelines_walnut_spreads_1.pdf

EN	Herbal Pacifier - Lombardia - Italy (English)	Project deliverable	Multiplier	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioco/projects-results/rigs/alpbioco_wp-t4_regional-implementation-guidelines_herbs_lombardia_itkam_engl_v1.pdf
IT	Herbal Pacifier - Lombardia - Italy (Italian)	Project deliverable	Multiplier	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioco/projects-results/rigs/alpbioco_wp-t4_regional-implementation-guidelines_herbs_lombardia_itkam_ital_v1.pdf
EN	Herbal Pacifier - Slovenia (English)	Project deliverable	Multiplier	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioco/projects-results/rigs/alpbioco_wp-t4_rig_herbs-ccis-cafe_en_v1.pdf
SL	Herbal Pacifier - Slovenia (Slovenian)	Project deliverable	Multiplier	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioco/projects-results/rigs/alpbioco_wp-t4_rig_herbs-ccis-cafe_si_v1.pdf
EN	Revegetation with Alpine hay seeds - Voralberg - Austria (English)	Project deliverable	Multiplier	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioco/projects-results/rigs/alpbioco_wp-t4_regional-implementation-guidelines_riw-alpine-hay-seeds_english_v1.pdf
DE	Revegetation with Alpine hay seeds - Voralberg - Austria (German)	Project deliverable	Multiplier	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioco/projects-results/rigs/alpbioco_wp-t4_regional-implementation-guidelines_riw-magerwiesensaatgut_deutsch_v1.pdf
EN	Digital service platform - Bavaria - Germany (English)	Project deliverable	Multiplier	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioco/projects-results/rigs/alpbioco_wp-t4_rig_digital-service-platform_english_kern_final_v1.pdf
DE	Digital service platform - Bavaria - Germany (German)	Project deliverable	Multiplier	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioco/projects-results/rigs/alpbioco_wp-t4_rig_digital-ernetzungsplattform_dt_kern_v1.pdf
EN	Transregional and transnational transfer guideline (English)	Project deliverable	Multiplier	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioco/projects-results/wpt4/alpbioco_transregional-and-transnationaltransfer-guideline_2021_web.pdf
EN	AlpBioEco final report (English)	Project progress/final report	Multiplier	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioco/projects-results/final-report-factsheets/final-report-en/hsa-abe-final-report-bl_weblinks.pdf
SL	AlpBioEco final report (Slovenian)	Project progress/final report	Multiplier	AlpBioEco	https://www.alpine-space.eu/projects/alpbioco/projects-results/final-report-translated/hsa-abe-final-report-bl_si_low_1-page-view.pdf
EN	Smart Atlas	Database or repository	Multiplier	Askfood	https://www.askfood.eu/tools/smart-atlas/maps/
EN	Forecast Aggregator	Platform	Multiplier	Askfood	https://www.askfood.eu/tools/forecast/forecast/
EN	Interactive Training Gap Identifier - Career Maps	Platform	Demand	Askfood	https://www.askfood.eu/tools/itqi/index.php/career-maps/
EN	New professions in the food sector	Project deliverable	Demand	Askfood	https://www.askfood.eu/tools/itqi/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/NEW-PROFESSIONS-WEB-last-version.pdf
EN	TOOL3-Overview of Generic Skills and Competences (GSC)	Project deliverable	Demand	Askfood	https://www.askfood.eu/tools/itqi/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/05.01.21-TOOL-3-Get-familiar-with-the-General-Skills-ASKFOOD_GSC-Overview.pdf
EN	Digital Game-Based Learning in the Agrifood Training	Presentation	Multiplier	Askfood	https://www.askfood.eu/sites/default/files/Wardaszko_Underscore_Presentation.pdf
EN	Report on Market Outlook and Future Viability of Different Bioenergy Products and Value Chains in the Baltic Sea Region Energy System	Project deliverable	Supply	BalticBiomass4Value	https://balticbiomass4value.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/BB4V_A_2.1_REPORT_17.10.2019_V2_FOR_WEB.pdf
EN	Analysis on market outlook and future viability of different bioenergy products and value chains in the Baltic Sea Region energy system	Presentation	Multiplier	BalticBiomass4Value	https://balticbiomass4value.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/Tr%C3%B8mborg.pdf
EN	Report on the mapping of biomass value chains for improved sustainable energy use in the Baltic Sea Region countries	Project deliverable	Multiplier	BalticBiomass4Value	https://balticbiomass4value.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/BB4V_A_2.2_REPORT_01.09.2020_FOR_WEB.pdf
EN	Biomass potential and its deployment opportunities in countries of the Baltic Sea Region	Presentation	Multiplier	BalticBiomass4Value	https://balticbiomass4value.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/07-Mariusz-Stolarski.pdf
EN	Vital ingredients and regional hotspots for successful entrepreneurship and business in rural areas	Presentation	Multiplier	BalticBiomass4Value	https://balticbiomass4value.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/Grundmann.pdf
EN	Mapping biomass value chains for improved sustainable energy use in the Baltic Sea Region	Presentation	Multiplier	BalticBiomass4Value	https://balticbiomass4value.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/Krzy%C5%BCaniak.pdf
EN	AGENCY FOR RENEWABLE RESOURCES	Presentation	Multiplier	BalticBiomass4Value	https://balticbiomass4value.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/Piedra-Garcia.pdf

EN	Current trends on Business Models and Biomass: A Literature Review	Presentation	Multiplier	BalticBiomass4Value	https://balticbiomass4value.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/Ulvenblad.pdf
EN	Putting paludiculture into practice Integration - Management - Cultivation (Paludi-PRIMA)	Presentation	Multiplier	BalticBiomass4Value	https://balticbiomass4value.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/Vogel.pdf
EN	The ENERGY BARGE modal shift platform and its transferability to other projects as a decision support tool	Presentation	Multiplier	BalticBiomass4Value	https://balticbiomass4value.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/Dorner.pdf
LT	Bioekonomikos plėtros perspektyvos Europoje ir Lietuvoje	Publication	Multiplier	BalticBiomass4Value	https://balticbiomass4value.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/Bioekonomikos_perspektyvos_LBTA_2020_05_29_galut.pdf
EN	Report on Good Practice Business Models and Example Small and Medium Scale Pilot Business Projects for Sustainable Bioenergy and Side Bio-products Production in the BSR	Project deliverable	Multiplier	BalticBiomass4Value	https://balticbiomass4value.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/BB4V_A_2.3_REPORT_15.01.2021_FOR_WEB.pdf
EN	Business model innovation for biomass development: A Literature Review	Presentation	Multiplier	BalticBiomass4Value	https://balticbiomass4value.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/4_Henrik_Barth_Sweden.pdf
EN	Lithuanian priorities for the development of bioeconomy (bioresources and biomass)	Presentation	Multiplier	BalticBiomass4Value	https://balticbiomass4value.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/1_Dalia_Minaitaite_Lithuania.pdf
EN	Developing bioeconomy in Latvia	Presentation	Multiplier	BalticBiomass4Value	https://balticbiomass4value.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/2_Irina_Pilvere_Latvia.pdf
EN	Developing bioeconomy in Estonia	Presentation	Multiplier	BalticBiomass4Value	https://balticbiomass4value.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/3_Arqa_Peepson_Estonia.pdf
EN	Educational materials on sustainability, circular economy and bioeconomy for schools, colleges and universities	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/Educational-materials-on-sustainability-word-version-v2_reduced.pdf
EN	Annex V – Output 1: Review of 100 free online teaching resources (listed by theme: bioeconomy, circular economy & SDGs)	Database or repository	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/Annex-V-Review-of-100-free-online-teaching-resources.pdf
EN	Introduction to the bioeconomy	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/annex-vi-power-point-slides-and-notes-on-introduction-to-the-bioeconomy-v3-2/
EN	Bioeconomy and key principles of sustainability	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/annex-vii-power-point-slides-and-notes-on-bioeconomy-and-key-principles-of-sustainability-v3-2/
EN	Bioeconomy and SDGs (and respective targets)	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/annex-viii-power-point-slides-and-notes-on-bioeconomy-and-sdgs-and-respective-targets-v3-2/
EN	Bioeconomy and the Circular Economy	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/annex-ix-power-point-slides-and-notes-on-bioeconomy-and-the-circular-economy-v3-2/
EN	Bioeconomy in the agriculture sector	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/annex-x-power-point-slides-and-notes-on-bioeconomy-in-the-agriculture-sector-v3-2/
EN	Bioeconomy in the forestry sector	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/annex-xi-power-point-slides-and-notes-on-bioeconomy-in-the-forestry-sector-v3-2/
EN	Bioeconomy in the fisheries sector	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/annex-xii-power-point-slides-and-notes-on-bioeconomy-in-the-fisheries-sector-v3-2/
EN	Bioeconomy in the sector of essential oils and herbs for cosmetics/pharmaceuticals	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/annex-xiii-power-point-slides-and-notes-on-bioeconomy-in-the-sector-of-essential-oils-and-herbs-for-cosmetics-pharmaceuticals-v3-2/
EN	Annex XIV – Mentimeter Ideas	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/Annex-XIV-Mentimeter-ideas.pdf
EN	Annex XV Workshop and Card Game “Business Match”	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/Annex-XV-Workshop-and-Card-Game-22Business-Match22.pdf
EN	Annex XVI Game “Sustainability and SDGs Heatwave”	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/Annex-XVI-Game-22Sustainability-and-SDGs-Heatwave22.pdf
EN	Annex XVII One set of cards and two games: “BE-Match” and “SDG-Link”	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/Annex-XVII-One-set-of-cards-and-two-games_22BE-Match22-22SDG-Link22.pdf
EN	Annex XVIII Bioeconomy Word Search Puzzles	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/Annex-XVIII-Bioeconomy-Word-Search-Puzzles.pdf

EN	Sustainability and Participation in the Bioeconomy: A Conceptual Framework for BE-Rural	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/D1.1_Conceptual_Framework.pdf
EN	Small-scale technology options for regional bioeconomies	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/BE-Rural_D2.1_Small-scale_technology_options.pdf
EN	The macro-environment surrounding BE-Rural's Open Innovation Platforms	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/BE-Rural_D2.2_Macro-environment_OIPs.pdf
EN	The bioeconomy potential of BE-Rural's OIP regions	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/BE-Rural_D2.3_Bioeconomy_potential_analysis.pdf
EN	Business models for regional bioeconomies	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/BE-Rural_D2.4_Regional_business_models.pdf
EN	Handbook on regional and local bio-based economies	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/BE-Rural_D2.5_Handbook.pdf
BG	Наръчник за регионални и местни био-базирани икономики	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/BE-Rural_D2.5_Handbook_BG.pdf
LV	Lauku un reģionālās bioekonomikas rokasgrāmata	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/BE-Rural_D2.5_Handbook_LV.pdf
MK	Прирачник за регионални и локални био-базирани економики	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/BE-Rural_D2.5_Handbook_MK.pdf
PL	Podręcznik na temat regionalnych i lokalnych bio gospodarek opartych o zasoby	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/BE-Rural_D2.5_Handbook_PL.pdf
RO	Manual privind bioeconomii regionale și locale	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/BE-Rural_D2.5_Handbook_RO.pdf
DE	Handbuch Regionale und lokale Bioökonomien	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/BE-Rural_D2.5_Handbook_GER.pdf
EN	Briefing paper: Concept for a pop-up store with bio-based products and participatory events	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/BE-Rural_D3.1_Bio-based_Pop-up_Store.pdf
BG	Образователни материали за устойчивост, кръгова икономика и биоикономика за училища, колежи и университети	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/Educational-materials-BG-Final.pdf
RO	Materiale didactice în domeniul dezvoltării durabile, al economiei circulare și al bioeconomiei destinate învățământului primar, secundar și terțiar	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/0089_Educational-materials-on-sustainability-word-version-v2_RO_rev1.pdf
MK	Едукативни материјали за одржливост, циркуларна економија и биономија за основни и средни училишта и университети	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/Educational-materials-on-sustainability-circular-economy-and-bioeconomy-for-schools-colleges-and-universities_MK.pdf
EN	Briefing paper: Knowledge exchange and capacity building for the bioeconomy in rural areas	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/BE-Rural_D4.1_Knowledge_Exchange_Capacity_Building.pdf
EN	Briefing paper: Analysing market conditions and designing business models within BE-Rural's OIPs	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/BE-Rural_D5.1_Market_conditions_business_models.pdf
BG	Приложение V - Резултат 1: Преглед на 100 безплатни онлайн учебни ресурси (изброени по теми: биоикономика, кръгова икономика и ЦУР)	Database or repository	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/%D0%9F%D1%80%D0%B8%D0%BB%D0%BE%D0%B6%D0%B5%D0%BD%D0%B8%D0%B5-V.pdf
MK	Прилог V – Аутпут 1: Преглед на 100 бесплатни онлајн едукативни материјали (наведени според тема: биономија, циркуларна економија и ЦОП)	Database or repository	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/%D0%9F%D1%80%D0%B8%D0%BB%D0%BE%D0%B3-V.pdf
PL	Aneks V – Rezultat 1: Przegląd 100 darmowych zasobów dydaktycznych online (wymienionych według tematów: biogospodarka, gospodarka cyrkularna i SDGs)	Database or repository	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Aneks-V.pdf

RO	Anexa V –Produsul 1: 100 de resurse educaționale gratuite online, analizate (enumerate după subiect: bioeconomie, economia circulară și ODD	Database or repository	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Anexa-V.pdf
LV	Pielikums Nr. V – 1. rezultāts: 100 bezmaksas tiešsaistes izglītības resursu pārskats (uzskaitījums atbilstoši nosaukumam: bioekonomika, aprites ekonomika un IAM)	Database or repository	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Annex-V-Review-of-100-free-online-teaching-resources-Lat.pdf
BG	Въведение в биоикономиката / Introduction to the bioeconomy	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/annex-vi-introduction-to-the-bioeconomy-bg/
BG	Биоикономика и ключови принципи на устойчивост / Bioeconomy and key principles of sustainability	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/annex-vii-bioeconomy-and-key-principles-of-sustainability-bg/
BG	Биоикономика и ЦУР / Bioeconomy and SDGs	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/annex-viii-bioeconomy-and-sdgs-and-respective-targets-bg/
BG	Биоикономиката и кръговата икономика / Bioeconomy and the circular economy	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/annex-ix-bioeconomy-and-the-circular-economy-bg/
BG	Биоикономика в селскостопанския сектор / Bioeconomy in the agriculture sector	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/annex-x-bioeconomy-in-the-agriculture-sector-bg/
BG	Биоикономика в горския сектор / Bioeconomy in the forestry sector	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/annex-xi-bioeconomy-in-the-forestry-sector-bg/
BG	Биоикономика в сектора на рибарството / Bioeconomy in the fisheries sector	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/annex-xii-bioeconomy-in-the-fisheries-sector-bg/
BG	Биоикономика в сектора на етерични масла и билки за козметика и фармацевтика / Bioeconomy in the sector of essential oils and herbs for cosmetics and pharmaceuticals	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/annex-xiii-bioeconomy-in-the-sector-of-essential-oils-and-herbs-for-cosmetics-pharmaceuticals-bg/
BG	Идеи за Mentimeter / Mentimeter ideas	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/%D0%9F%D1%80%D0%B8%D0%BB%D0%BE%D0%B6%D0%B5%D0%BD%D0%B8%D0%B5-XIV.pdf
BG	Семинар и игра на карти „Бизнес съвпадение“ / Workshop and Card Game “Business Match”	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/%D0%9F%D1%80%D0%B8%D0%BB%D0%BE%D0%B6%D0%B5%D0%BD%D0%B8%D0%B5-XV.pdf
BG	Игра „Устойчивост и топлинна вълна на ЦУР“ / Game “Sustainability and SDGs Heatwave”	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/%D0%9F%D1%80%D0%B8%D0%BB%D0%BE%D0%B6%D0%B5%D0%BD%D0%B8%D0%B5-XVI.pdf
BG	Един комплект карти и две игри: “BE-Match” и “SDG-Link” / One set of cards and two games: “BE-Match” and “SDG-Link”	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/%D0%9F%D1%80%D0%B8%D0%BB%D0%BE%D0%B6%D0%B5%D0%BD%D0%B8%D0%B5-XVII.pdf
BG	Пъзели за търсене на думи за биоикономиката / Bioeconomy Word Search Puzzles	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/%D0%9F%D1%80%D0%B8%D0%BB%D0%BE%D0%B6%D0%B5%D0%BD%D0%B8%D0%B5-XVIII.pdf
BG	Доклад за BE-Rural образователни материали / Report on BE-Rural Educational Material	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/educational-materials-bg-final/
MK	Вовед во биоикономијата / Introduction to the bioeconomy	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/2_Annex-VI-Power-Point-slides-and-notes-on-Introduction-to-the-bioeconomy-v3-%D0%9C%D0%9A.pptx
MK	Биоикономија и клучни принципи на одржливост / Bioeconomy and key principles of sustainability	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/3_Annex-VII-Power-Point-slides-and-notes-on-Bioeconomy-and-key-principles-of-sustainability-v3-%D0%9C%D0%9A.pptx
MK	Биоикономија и SDG / Bioeconomy and SDGs	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/4_Annex-VIII-Power-Point-slides-and-notes-on-Bioeconomy-and-SDGs-and-respective-targets-v3-%D0%9C%D0%9A.pptx

MK	Биекономија и циркуларна економија / Bioeconomy and the circular economy	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/5_Annex-IX-Power-Point-slides-and-notes-on-Bioeconomy-and-the-Circular-Economy_v3-%D0%9C%D0%9A-1.pptx
MK	Биекономија во земјоделскиот сектор / Bioeconomy in the agriculture sector	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/6_Annex-X-Power-Point-slides-and-notes-on-Bioeconomy-in-the-agriculture-sector_v3-%D0%9C%D0%9A.pptx
MK	Биекономија во секторот шумарство / Bioeconomy in the forestry sector	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/7_Annex-XI-Power-Point-slides-and-notes-on-Bioeconomy-in-the-forestry-sector_v3-%D0%9C%D0%9A.pptx
MK	Биекономија во рибарскиот сектор / Bioeconomy in the fisheries sector	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/8_Annex-XII-Power-Point-slides-and-notes-on-Bioeconomy-in-the-fisheries-sector_v3-%D0%9C%D0%9A.pptx
MK	Биекономија во секторот за козметика и фармацевтски производи (есенцијални масла и билки) / Bioeconomy in the sector of essential oils and herbs for cosmetics and pharmaceuticals	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/9_Annex-XIII-Power-Point-slides-and-notes-on-Bioeconomy-in-the-sector-of-essential-oils-and-herbs-for-cosmetics_pharmaceuticals_V3-%D0%9C%D0%9A.pptx
MK	Идеи за Mentimeter / Mentimeter ideas	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/%D0%9F%D1%80%D0%B8%D0%BB%D0%BE%D0%B3-XIV.pdf
MK	Работилница и игра со карти „Спарување на бизниси“ / Workshop and Card Game “Business Match”	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/%D0%9F%D1%80%D0%B8%D0%BB%D0%BE%D0%B3-XV.pdf
MK	Игра „Одржливост и топлотен бран на ЦОП“ / Game “Sustainability and SDGs Heatwave”	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/%D0%9F%D1%80%D0%B8%D0%BB%D0%BE%D0%B3-XVI.pdf
MK	Еден комплет карти и две игри: „Спарување со БЕ“ и „Поврзување со ЦОП“ / One set of cards and two games: “BE-Match” and “SDG-Link”	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/%D0%9F%D1%80%D0%B8%D0%BB%D0%BE%D0%B3-XVII.pdf
MK	Осмисмерки за биекономија / Bioeconomy Word Search Puzzles	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/%D0%9F%D1%80%D0%B8%D0%BB%D0%BE%D0%B3-XVIII.pdf
MK	Извештај за BE-Rural едукативен материјал / Report on BE-Rural Educational Material	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/1_Educational-materials-on-sustainability-word-version-v2_reduced-%D0%9C%D0%9A.pdf
PL	Wprowadzenie do biogospodarki / Introduction to the bioeconomy	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Annex-VI-Power-Point-slides-and-notes-on-Introduction-to-the-bioeconomy-v4_PL.pptx
PL	Biogospodarka i kluczowe zasady zrównoważonego rozwoju / Bioeconomy and key principles of sustainability	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Annex-VII-Power-Point-slides-and-notes-on-Bioeconomy-and-key-principles-of-sustainability-v4_PL.pptx
PL	Biogospodarka i SDGs / Bioeconomy and SDGs	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Annex-VIII-Power-Point-slides-and-notes-on-Bioeconomy-and-SDGs-and-respective-targets-v4_PL.pptx
PL	Biogospodarka i gospodarka cyrkulama / Bioeconomy and the circular economy	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Annex-IX-Power-Point-slides-and-notes-on-Bioeconomy-and-the-Circular-Economy-v4_PL.pptx
PL	Biogospodarka w sektorze rolnym / Bioeconomy in the agriculture sector	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Annex-X-Power-Point-slides-and-notes-on-Bioeconomy-in-the-agriculture-sector-v4_PL.pptx
PL	Biogospodarka w sektorze leśnym / Bioeconomy in the forestry sector	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Annex-XI-Power-Point-slides-and-notes-on-Bioeconomy-in-the-forestry-sector-v4_PL.pptx
PL	Biogospodarka w sektorze rybnym / Bioeconomy in the fisheries sector	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Annex-XII-Power-Point-slides-and-notes-on-Bioeconomy-in-the-fisheries-sector-v4_PL.pptx
PL	Biogospodarka w sektorze olejków eterycznych i ziół dla przemysłu kosmetycznego i farmaceutycznego / Bioeconomy in the sector of essential oils and herbs for cosmetics and pharmaceuticals	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Annex-XIII-Power-Point-slides-and-notes-on-Bioeconomy-in-the-sector-of-essential-oils-and-herbs-for-cosmetics-pharmaceuticals_V4_PL.pptx
PL	Pomysły na wykorzystanie aplikacji Mentimeter / Mentimeter ideas	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Annex-XIV-Mentimeter-ideas_PL.pdf
PL	Warsztaty i gra karciana “Business Match” / Workshop and Card Game “Business Match”	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Annex-XV.pdf

PL	Gra "Sustainability and SDGs Heatwave" / Game "Sustainability and SDGs Heatwave"	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Aneks-XVI.pdf
PL	Jeden zestaw kart i dwie gry: "BE-Match" i "SDG-Link" / One set of cards and two games: "BE-Match" and "SDG-Link"	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Aneks-XVII.pdf
PL	Biogospodarka – Puzzle słowne / Bioeconomy Word Search Puzzles	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Aneks-XVIII.pdf
PL	Sprawozdanie dotyczące BE-Rural materiałów edukacyjnych / Report on BE-Rural Educational Material	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/educational-materials-on-sustainability-word-version-v2_reduced_pl/
RO	Introducere în bioeconomie / Introduction to the bioeconomy	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/Annex-VI-Power-Point-slides-and-notes-on-Introduction-to-the-bioeconomy_-v3_RO.pptx
RO	Bioeconomie și principiile cheie ale sustenabilității / Bioeconomy and key principles of sustainability	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/Annex-VII-Power-Point-slides-and-notes-on-Bioeconomy-and-key-principles-of-sustainability_-v3_RO.pptx
RO	Bioeconomie și ODD / Bioeconomy and SDGs	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/Annex-VIII-Power-Point-slides-and-notes-on-Bioeconomy-and-SDGs-and-respective-targets_-v3_RO.pptx
RO	Bioeconomia și economia circulară / Bioeconomy and the circular economy	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/Annex-IX-Power-Point-slides-and-notes-on-Bioeconomy-and-the-Circular-Economy_-v3_RO.pptx
RO	Bioeconomia în sectorul agricol / Bioeconomy in the agriculture sector	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/Annex-X-Power-Point-slides-and-notes-on-Bioeconomy-in-the-agriculture-sector_-v3_RO.pptx
RO	Bioeconomia în sectorul forestier / Bioeconomy in the forestry sector	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/Annex-XI-Power-Point-slides-and-notes-on-Bioeconomy-in-the-forestry-sector_-v3_RO.pptx
RO	Bioeconomia în sectorul pescuitului / Bioeconomy in the fisheries sector	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/Annex-XII-Power-Point-slides-and-notes-on-Bioeconomy-in-the-fisheries-sector_-v3_RO.pptx
RO	Bioeconomie în sectorul uleiurilor și ierburilor pentru produse cosmetice și farmaceutice / Bioeconomy in the sector of oils and herbs for cosmetics and pharmaceuticals	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/Annex-XIII-Power-Point-slides-and-notes-on-Bioeconomy-in-the-sector-of-essential-oils-and-herbs-for-cosmetics_pharmaceuticals_-V3_RO.pptx
RO	Ideii pentru Mentimeter / Mentimeter ideas	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Anexa-XIV.pdf
RO	Seminar și joc de cărți „Correspondența cu afacerea” / Workshop and Card Game “Business Match”	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Anexa-XV.pdf
RO	Jocul „Durabilitate și ODDuri – Valul de căldură” / Game “Sustainability and SDGs Heatwave”	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Anexa-XVI.pdf
RO	Un set de carduri și două jocuri: „Correspondența cu BE” și „Legătura cu ODD” / One set of cards and two games: “BE-Match” and “SDG-Link”	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Anexa-XVII.pdf
RO	Careuri de cuvinte încrucișate din bioeconomie / Bioeconomy Word Search Puzzles	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/Anexa-XVIII.pdf
RO	Raport privind BE-Rural materialul educațional / Report on BE-Rural Educational Material	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/0089_Educational-materials-on-sustainability-word-version-v2_RO_rev1.pdf
LV	Ievads bioekonomikā / Introduction to the bioeconomy	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Annex-VI_LAT.pptx
LV	Ilgspējības pamatprincipi un saikne ar bioekonomiku / Bioeconomy and key principles of sustainability	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Annex-VII_LAT.pptx
LV	Ievads ilgtspējīgas attīstības mērķos (IAM) un to saikne ar bioekonomiku / Bioeconomy and SDGs	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Annex-VIII_LAT.pptx
LV	Galvenie aprītes ekonomikas principi un saistība ar bioekonomiku / Bioeconomy and the circular economy	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Annex-IX_LAT.pptx

LV	Lauksaimniecība un bioekonomika / Bioeconomy in the agriculture sector	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Annex-X_LAT.pptx
LV	Meža bioekonomika / Bioeconomy in the forestry sector	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Annex-XI_LAT.pptx
LV	Bioekonomika zivsaimniecības nozarē / Bioeconomy in the fisheries sector	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Annex-XII_LAT.pptx
LV	Jaunas augu pārstrādes tehnoloģijas ēterisko eļļu ražošanai priekš kosmētikas un farmācijas nozarēm / Bioeconomy in the sector of essential oils and herbs for cosmetics and pharmaceuticals	Presentation	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Annex-XIII_LAT.pptx
LV	Mentimeter idejas / Mentimeter ideas	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Annex-XIV-Mentimeter-ideas-Lat.pdf
LV	Pamācība spēlei "Biznesa sakrītība" / Workshop and Card Game "Business Match"	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Annex-XV-Workshop-and-Card-Game-22Business-Match22-Lat.pdf
LV	Spēle "Ilgtspējas un IAM triecienviktorīna" – Noteikumi/ Game "Sustainability and SDGs Heatwave"	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Ilgtsp%C4%93jas-viktor%C4%ABnas-iaut%C4%81jumi.docx.pdf
LV	Kāršu spēle / One set of cards and two games: "BE-Match" and "SDG-Link"	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Annex-XVII-One-set-of-cards-and-two-games_22BE-Match22-22SDG-Link22-Lat.pdf
LV	Vieglāka vārdu meklēšana / Bioeconomy Word Search Puzzles	Games	Multiplier	Be-Rural	https://be-rural.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Vardu_meklesana.pdf
EN	THE EUROPEAN BIOECONOMY IN 2030 Delivering Sustainable Growth by addressing the Grand Societal Challenges	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Becoteps	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/the_european_bioeconomy_brochure.pdf
EN	BioRegional Toolkit	Platform	Multiplier	Berst	https://www.berst.eu/Platform.aspx
EN	Good Practices in selected bioeconomy sector clusters; a comparative analysis	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Berst	https://www.wecr.wur.nl/BerstPublications/D3.1%20GoodPracticesInSelectedBioeconomySectors_8June15.pdf
EN	Criteria and Indicators describing the regional bioeconomy	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Berst	https://www.wecr.wur.nl/BerstPublications/D1.1%20Criteria%20and%20Indicators%20describing%20Regional%20Bioeconomy%20(Oct%202014).pdf
EN	A representative set of case studies	Case Study	Multiplier	Berst	https://www.wecr.wur.nl/BerstPublications/D3.2%20RepresentativeSetOfCaseStudies%20(v1)_10June15.pdf
EN	Correlation of I&M with the Criteria developed in WP1 (WP2)	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Berst	https://www.wecr.wur.nl/BerstPublications/D2.3%20Correlation%20I&M%20and%20Criteria_3%20Dec14.pdf
EN	BIOECONOMY REGIONAL STRATEGY TOOLKIT THE BERST PROJECT	Publication	Multiplier	Berst	https://www.wecr.wur.nl/BerstPublications/Paper%20GuissonVanLeeuwenJuni14.pdf
EN	Berst COP3 Terneuzen (NL)	Presentation	Multiplier	Berst	https://www.wecr.wur.nl/BerstPublications/D5.16%20CoP3%20Terneuzen%20(NL)%20Reflection%20Report.pdf
EN	BERST How to build Regional Bioeconomies and create new cross-sectoral business?	Presentation	Multiplier	Berst	https://www.wecr.wur.nl/BerstPublications/BERST_BrusselsSymposium_12Nov14.pdf
EN	Exploring the Importance of regional partnerships	Presentation	Multiplier	Berst	https://www.wecr.wur.nl/BerstPublications/3pptWillem%20key%20note.pdf
EN	BERST How to build Regional Bioeconomies and new agricultural entrepreneurship?	Presentation	Multiplier	Berst	https://www.wecr.wur.nl/BerstPublications/20140919_Kranendonk_Berst.pdf
EN	BioEconomy Regional Strategy Toolkit – CoP2	Presentation	Multiplier	Berst	https://www.wecr.wur.nl/BerstPublications/D5.10%20CoP2%20Ljubljana%20Reflection%20Report.pdf
EN	Bio Base NWE for Policy Makers and Advisors	Video	Multiplier	Bio Base NWE	https://youtu.be/84UYj4uC3P4
EN	BIOECONOMY FACTSHEET BELGIUM	Fact Sheet	Supply	Bio Base NWE	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/BBNWE-Factsheet-BE_Sept15_Final.pdf
EN	BIOECONOMY FACTSHEET EU	Fact Sheet	Supply	Bio Base NWE	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/BBNWE-Factsheet-EU_Sept15_Final.pdf
EN	BIOECONOMY FACTSHEET GERMANY	Fact Sheet	Supply	Bio Base NWE	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/BBNWE-Factsheet-DE_Sept15_Final.pdf

EN	BIOECONOMY FACTSHEET IRELAND	Fact Sheet	Supply	Bio Base NWE	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/BBNWE-Factsheet-IE_Sept15_Final.pdf
EN	BIOECONOMY FACTSHEET THE NETHERLANDS	Fact Sheet	Supply	Bio Base NWE	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/BBNWE-Factsheet-NL_Sept15_Final.pdf
EN	BIOECONOMY FACTSHEET UK	Fact Sheet	Supply	Bio Base NWE	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/BBNWE-Factsheet-UK_Sept15_Final.pdf
EN	Bio-Art Gallery Panels	Other	Demand, Multiplier	Bio-Art Gallery	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/BioArt_Gallery_high.pdf
EN	Territorial Forestry Charter (CFT)	Good practice	Multiplier	Bio4Eco	https://www.interregeurope.eu/policylearning/good-practices/item/1873/territorial-forestry-charter-ctf/
EN	FOREST BIOMASS PLANT FOR THE PRODUCTION OF THERMAL ENERGY	Good practice	Multiplier	Bio4Eco	https://www.interregeurope.eu/policylearning/good-practices/item/1615/forest-biomass-plant-for-the-production-of-thermal-energy/
EN	AGRICULTURAL BIOMASS SYSTEM FOR THERMAL, ELECTRIC AND BIOGAS ENERGY PRODUCTION	Good practice	Multiplier	Bio4Eco	https://www.interregeurope.eu/policylearning/good-practices/item/1613/agricultural-biomass-system-for-thermal-electric-and-biogas-energy-production/
EN	Municipality Vransko – active local bioenergy policy approach	Good practice	Multiplier	Bio4Eco	https://www.interregeurope.eu/policylearning/good-practices/item/1408/municipality-vransko-active-local-bioenergy-policy-approach/
EN	New production line for more effective use of forest biomass for production of heat energy	Good practice	Multiplier	Bio4Eco	https://www.interregeurope.eu/policylearning/good-practices/item/1396/new-production-line-for-more-effective-use-of-forest-biomass-for-production-of-heat-energy/
EN	Machinery circle Bled	Good practice	Multiplier	Bio4Eco	https://www.interregeurope.eu/policylearning/good-practices/item/1356/machinery-circle-bled/
EN	Functional land use management planning approach for bioeconomy development	Good practice	Multiplier	Bio4Eco	https://www.interregeurope.eu/policylearning/good-practices/item/1319/functional-land-use-management-planning-approach-for-bioeconomy-development/
EN	Low value forest stands replacement – improvement of biomass production	Good practice	Multiplier	Bio4Eco	https://www.interregeurope.eu/policylearning/good-practices/item/1206/low-value-forest-stands-replacement-improvement-of-biomass-production/
EN	Promoting biomass through a circular management processes at local scale in Berguedà county	Good practice	Multiplier	Bio4Eco	https://www.interregeurope.eu/policylearning/good-practices/item/1147/promoting-biomass-through-a-circular-management-processes-at-local-scale-in-bergueda-county/
EN	Knowledge transfer for creating eco-businesses along the value chain of the biomass	Good practice	Multiplier	Bio4Eco	https://www.interregeurope.eu/policylearning/good-practices/item/1137/knowledge-transfer-for-creating-eco-businesses-along-the-value-chain-of-the-biomass/
EN	Bioenergy villages	Good practice	Multiplier	Bio4Eco	https://www.interregeurope.eu/policylearning/good-practices/item/1006/bioenergy-villages/
EN	Forests of Vallès	Good practice	Multiplier	Bio4Eco	https://www.interregeurope.eu/policylearning/good-practices/item/979/forests-of-valles/
EN	Sirkkala Energy Park –a learning, RD&I and service environment for bioeconomy	Good practice	Multiplier	Bio4Eco	https://www.interregeurope.eu/policylearning/good-practices/item/953/sirkkala-energy-park-a-learning-rd-i-and-service-environment-for-bioeconomy/
EN	GreenHUB - solves challenges faced by companies	Good practice	Multiplier	Bio4Eco	https://www.interregeurope.eu/policylearning/good-practices/item/782/greenhub-solves-challenges-faced-by-companies/
EN	Business concept of Eno Energy Co-operative- district heating from local sustainable forest resources	Good practice	Multiplier	Bio4Eco	https://www.interregeurope.eu/policylearning/good-practices/item/678/business-concept-of-eno-energy-co-operative-district-heating-from-local-sustainable-forest-resources/
EN	Territorial biomass supply plan (PAT)	Good practice	Multiplier	Bio4Eco	https://www.interregeurope.eu/policylearning/good-practices/item/548/territorial-biomass-supply-plan-pat/
EN	POLICY BRIEF - V SEMESTER - NORTH KARELIA	Policy Brief	Multiplier	Bio4Eco	https://www.interregeurope.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/tx_tevprojects/library/file_1538053272.pdf
EN	POLICY BRIEF BULGARIA EXECUTIVE FOREST AGENCY	Policy Brief	Multiplier	Bio4Eco	https://www.interregeurope.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/tx_tevprojects/library/file_1501686701.pdf
EN	POLICY BRIEF 3RD SEMESTRE – CATALONIA	Policy Brief	Multiplier	Bio4Eco	https://www.interregeurope.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/tx_tevprojects/library/file_1507306206.pdf
EN	POLICY BRIEF 5TH SEMESTER –CENTRU REGION	Policy Brief	Multiplier	Bio4Eco	https://www.interregeurope.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/tx_tevprojects/library/file_1532512375.pdf

IT	ANALISI DEGLI STRUMENTI FINALIZZATI ALLA PROMOZIONE DI IMPIANTI DI PRODUZIONE DI ENERGIA DA BIOMASSE NELLA REGIONE ABRUZZO	Publication	Multiplier	Bio4Eco	https://www.interregeurope.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/tx_tevprojects/library/file_1507133431.pdf
EN	BACKGROUND STUDY ANALYSIS FOR NATIONAL BIOECONOMY STRATEGY LATVIA	Publication	Multiplier	Bio4Eco	https://www.interregeurope.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/tx_tevprojects/library/file_1504269344.pdf
ES	EL SECTOR DE LA BIOMASSA A CATALUNYA	Publication	Multiplier	Bio4Eco	https://www.interregeurope.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/tx_tevprojects/library/file_1504711821.pdf
FR	PANORAMA NATIONAL DES ENJEUX FORESTIERS DANS LES PLANS CLIMAT AIR ENERGIE TERRITORIAUX	Publication	Multiplier	Bio4Eco	https://www.interregeurope.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/tx_tevprojects/library/file_1505900756.pdf
BG	АНАЛИЗ на действащите европейски политики и регулации за горите и горското стопанство, имащи отношение към използването на биомасата за производство на топло и електроенергия	Publication	Multiplier	Bio4Eco	https://www.interregeurope.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/tx_tevprojects/library/file_1503571599.pdf
RO	ANALIZA EVOLUTIEI POLITICILOR REGIONALE, NATIONALEŞ I EUROPENE PRIVIND BIOENERGIAŞ I PRODUCEREA DE ENERGIE PRIN UTILIZAREA BIOMASEI	Publication	Multiplier	Bio4Eco	https://www.interregeurope.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/tx_tevprojects/library/file_1504270036.pdf
SL	Študija in analiza stanja potencialov, proizvodnje lesne biomase ter politik povezanihs proizvodnjo in rabo lesne biomase v Sloveniji	Publication	Multiplier	Bio4Eco	https://www.interregeurope.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/tx_tevprojects/library/file_1505900805.pdf
FI	Tiekartta öljyvapaaseen ja vähähiiliseen Pohjois-Karjalaan 2040	Publication	Multiplier	Bio4Eco	https://www.interregeurope.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/tx_tevprojects/library/file_1504697228.pdf
EN	Life Cycle Assessment on a Biorefinery Approach to Pyrolysis Oil for Wood Modification Treatment	Publication	Multiplier	Bio4Products	https://bio4products.eu/download/1804/
EN	Creating sustainable resources for processing industry - Journal of Industrial and Environmental Chemistry	Publication	Multiplier	Bio4Products	https://bio4products.eu/download/1662/
EN	Chemical composition of ten biomass feedstocks and their suitability for conversion by fast pyrolysis	Publication	Multiplier	Bio4Products	https://bio4products.eu/download/1635/
EN	Sustainability and lifecycle assessment of pyrolysis oil production and applications	Publication	Multiplier	Bio4Products	https://bio4products.eu/download/1526/
EN	Virtual Pyrolysis Plant Locations: Availability and quality of biomass at four potential sites	Publication	Multiplier	Bio4Products	https://bio4products.eu/download/1471/
EN	Melike Bayram_ Resins and moulding compounds from lignin	Presentation	Supply	Bio4Products	https://bio4products.eu/download/2050/
EN	Matthias Stratmann_ Sustainability in the bioeconomy	Presentation	Multiplier	Bio4Products	https://bio4products.eu/download/1966/
EN	Jurjen Spekrijse_ Sustainability of products from pyrolysis oil	Presentation	Multiplier	Bio4Products	https://bio4products.eu/download/1963/
EN	Nils Rettenmaier_ Green light for bio-based products?	Presentation	Multiplier	Bio4Products	https://bio4products.eu/download/1960/
EN	Kathryn Sheridan_ Credible communications	Presentation	Multiplier	Bio4Products	https://bio4products.eu/download/1957/
EN	Bart Tambuyser_ Virtual Pyrolysis Plant Locations	Presentation	Multiplier	Bio4Products	https://bio4products.eu/download/1877/
EN	Lars Wietschel_ Agroforestry residue potentials in the EU	Presentation	Multiplier	Bio4Products	https://bio4products.eu/download/1875/
EN	Sonja Germer_ Innovations in lignocellulosic biomass production	Presentation	Multiplier	Bio4Products	https://bio4products.eu/download/1873/
EN	Hans Heeres_ Thermo-Chemical Fractionation	Presentation	Multiplier	Bio4Products	https://bio4products.eu/download/1871/
EN	Paul de Wild_ Fractional condensation of vapours	Presentation	Multiplier	Bio4Products	https://bio4products.eu/download/1869/

EN	Gerhard Muggen_Market status of pyrolysis plants	Presentation	Multiplier	Bio4Products	https://bio4products.eu/download/1867/
EN	Frederik Ronsse_Introduction to fast pyrolysis Sustainable Process Industry (SPIRE) conference 2017	Presentation	Multiplier	Bio4Products	https://bio4products.eu/download/1836/
EN	Joint strategy and action plan containing policy recommendations to stimulate the bio-based economy in North West Europe	Project deliverable	Multiplier	BioBase4SME	https://www.nweurope.eu/media/7098/biobase4sme_action-plan-on-needs-of-smes-in-nweurope.pdf
EN	Needs and challenges of companies in the bioeconomy in NW Europe	Project deliverable	Multiplier	BioBase4SME	https://www.nweurope.eu/media/8950/needs-and-challenges_final_2019.pdf
FR	L'acceptabilité sociale	Training Material	Multiplier	BioBase4SME	https://www.nweurope.eu/media/4665/guide-acceptabilite-C3%A9-sociale-fr.pdf
EN	Bioeconomy Factsheet Belgium	Fact Sheet	Multiplier	BioBase4SME	https://www.nweurope.eu/media/4659/180369_biobase4sme_2luik_belgium_v4_lr.pdf
EN	Bioeconomy Factsheet France	Fact Sheet	Multiplier	BioBase4SME	https://www.nweurope.eu/media/4660/180369_biobase4sme_2luik_france_v3_lr.pdf
EN	Bioeconomy Factsheet Germany	Fact Sheet	Multiplier	BioBase4SME	https://www.nweurope.eu/media/4661/180369_biobase4sme_2luik_germany_v8_lr.pdf
EN	Bioeconomy Factsheet Ireland	Fact Sheet	Multiplier	BioBase4SME	https://www.nweurope.eu/media/4662/180369_biobase4sme_2luik_ireland_v4_lr.pdf
EN	Bioeconomy Factsheet Luxembourg	Fact Sheet	Multiplier	BioBase4SME	https://www.nweurope.eu/media/5602/180919_biobase4sme-2luik_luxembourg_lr.pdf
EN	Bioeconomy Factsheet The Netherlands	Fact Sheet	Multiplier	BioBase4SME	https://www.nweurope.eu/media/4663/180369_biobase4sme_2luik_netherlands_v4_lr.pdf
EN	Bioeconomy Factsheet United Kingdom	Fact Sheet	Multiplier	BioBase4SME	https://www.nweurope.eu/media/4664/180369_biobase4sme_2luik_uk_v4_lr.pdf
EN	Bioeconomy Factsheet Switzerland	Fact Sheet	Multiplier	BioBase4SME	https://www.nweurope.eu/media/5603/180919_biobase4sme-2luik_switzerland_lr.pdf
EN	Social Acceptance Developing dialogue with your stakeholders	Training Material	Multiplier	BioBase4SME	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/social-acceptance-guide-pdf-version_22032018.pdf
EN	"A bio-based day" video	Video	Demand	Biobridges	https://www.biobridges-project.eu/results/a-bio-based-day-video
EN	BioHeroes	Platform	Multiplier	Biobridges	https://www.biobridges-project.eu/about/#bioheroes
EN	Biobridges Consultation infographic	Infographics	Multiplier	Biobridges	https://www.biobridges-project.eu/results/biobridges-consultation/
EN	Bridge2Value	Other	Multiplier	Biobridges	https://www.biobridges-project.eu/news-events/news/create-new-value-chains-in-5-steps-the-bridge2value-methodology/
EN	Bridge2Brands	Other	Multiplier	Biobridges	https://www.biobridges-project.eu/news-events/news/bridge2brands-an-innovative-format-to-connect-brands-and-bio-based-solution-providers/
EN	BIOBRIDGES Framework for mapping Collaboration Challenges among stakeholders	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Biobridges	https://www.biobridges-project.eu/en/results/cooperation-challenges-among-consumers-brand-owners-and-bio-based-industry/
EN	Biobridges communication toolkit	Other	Multiplier	Biobridges	https://www.biobridges-project.eu/results/bio-based-economy-awareness-toolkit/
EN	Best practices and challenges on multi-stakeholder and cross sector interconnections	Fact Sheet	Multiplier	Biobridges	https://www.biobridges-project.eu/en/results/factsheet-best-practices-and-challenges-on-cross-sector-interconnections/
EN	BIOBRIDGES PLATFORM design: WHAT, WHO and HOW	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Biobridges	https://www.biobridges-project.eu/results/biobridges-platform-design-what-who-and-how/
EN	BIOBRIDGES's policy paper	Recommendation	Multiplier	Biobridges	https://www.biobridges-project.eu/news-events/news/policy-paper/
EN	Best practices & challenges in multi-stakeholder and cross-sector interconnections	Infographics	Multiplier	Biobridges	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/infographic_best-practices-challenges_20192110_1021070927.pdf
EN	Framework and good practices for multi-stakeholder and cross-sector interconnections	Good practice	Multiplier	Biobridges	https://www.biobridges-project.eu/results/framework-and-good-practices-for-multi-stakeholder-and-cross-sector-interconnections/
EN	Communication needs in the bio-based economy	Infographics	Multiplier	Biobridges	https://www.biobridges-project.eu/en/results/communication-needs-in-the-bio-based-economy/
EN	Serious game – Concept and objectives	project deliverable	Multiplier	Biobridges	https://www.biobridges-project.eu/en/results/serious-game-concept-and-objectives/
EN	Recommendations to enhance collaboration among industry, brand owners and consumers	Recommendation	Multiplier	Biobridges	https://www.biobridges-project.eu/en/results/recommendations-to-enhance-collaboration-among-industry-brand-owners-and-consumers/
EN	Factsheet – Drivers and barriers faced by brands related with the adoption of bio-based business models	Fact Sheet	Multiplier	Biobridges	https://www.biobridges-project.eu/en/results/factsheet-drivers-and-barriers-faced-by-brands/

EN	Factsheet – Current and future trends and barriers faced by the bio-based industry	Fact Sheet	Supply	Biobridges	https://www.biobridges-project.eu/en/results/factsheet-trends-and-barriers-for-the-bio-based-industry/
EN	Factsheet – Challenges in the cooperation between Industry and feedstock suppliers from the industry point of view	Fact Sheet	Supply	Biobridges	https://www.biobridges-project.eu/en/results/factsheet-challenges-in-the-cooperation/
EN	Cross-sectoral and multi-stakeholder collaboration - the way to ensure a sustainable bioeconomy for Europe	project deliverable	Multiplier	Biobridges	https://www.biobridges-project.eu/en/results/cross-sectoral-and-multi-stakeholder-collaboration/
EN	Proceedings from EU, national and regional co-creation events and policy debates - 3rd Period	project deliverable	Multiplier	Biobridges	https://www.biobridges-project.eu/en/results/proceedings-from-the-european-national-and-regional-co-creation-events/
EN	Glossary table	Other	Demand	BioCannDo	https://www.allthings.bio/keywords/
EN	Links - Online resources about the bioeconomy and bio-based products	Database or repository	Demand	BioCannDo	https://www.allthings.bio/resources/
EN	Bio-based household cleaning products	Presentation	Multiplier	BioCannDo	https://www.allthings.bio/pageflow/bio-based-household-cleaning-products/
EN	Bio-based Insulation Materials	Presentation	Multiplier	BioCannDo	https://www.allthings.bio/pageflow/bio-based-insulation-materials/
EN	Seven things to know about bioeconomy	Fact Sheet	Multiplier	BioCannDo	http://www.allthings.bio/wp-content/uploads/2018/09/Key-messages_General.pdf
EN	Bio-based household cleaning products	Fact Sheet	Multiplier	BioCannDo	http://www.allthings.bio/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/BioCannDo_Key-messages_Cleaning-products.pdf
EN	Bio-based insulation materials	Fact Sheet	Multiplier	BioCannDo	http://www.allthings.bio/wp-content/uploads/2018/09/Key-messages_insulation_11122018-1.pdf
EN	Bio-based food packaging	Fact Sheet	Multiplier	BioCannDo	http://www.allthings.bio/wp-content/uploads/2019/04/Key-messages_food-packaging_ATB.pdf
EN	What people want to learn and know about bio-based products Communication topics & desired info	Fact Sheet	Multiplier	BioCannDo	http://www.allthings.bio/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/Factsheet-Communication-topics_v5_SR.pdf
EN	Engagement on Bioeconomy Good practices and lessons learned	Fact Sheet	Multiplier	BioCannDo	http://www.allthings.bio/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/Factsheet-Engagement-formats_v5_SR.pdf
EN	Bioeconomy exhibitions Good practices and lessons learned	Fact Sheet	Multiplier	BioCannDo	http://www.allthings.bio/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/Factsheet-Exhibitions_v5_SR.pdf
EN	Bio-based food packaging	Presentation	Multiplier	BioCannDo	https://www.allthings.bio/pageflow/bio-based-food-packaging/
EN	The BioCannDo experience: Let's talk about bio-based products - 10 Insights on communicating the bioeconomy	Publication	Multiplier	BioCannDo	http://www.allthings.bio/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/BCD-Final-publication-WEB.pdf
EN	AllThings.Bio Portal	Other	Demand, Multiplier	BioCannDo	https://www.allthings.bio/
EN	Teachers guide bioplastic street	Training material	Multiplier	BioCannDo, taken up by AllThings.Bio	http://www.allthings.bio/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/Manual-Bioplastic-Street.pdf
EN	The Fundamentals Of Bioeconomy The Biobased Society	Other	demand	BIOEASTSUP	https://bioeast.eu/download/the-fundamentals-of-bioeconomy-the-biobased-society/
EN	Policy Support Facility (PSF) 2 workshop	Presentation	Multiplier	BIOEASTSUP	https://bioeast.eu/download/policy-support-facility-psf-2-workshop/
EN	Advancing the Creation of Regional Bioeconomy Clusters in Europe workshop	Presentation	Multiplier	BIOEASTSUP	https://bioeast.eu/download/advancing-the-creation-of-regional-bioeconomy-clusters-in-europe-workshop/
EN	The Bioeconet project E-learning platform	Training Material	Demand	Bioecon	http://moodlebioecon.eu/
EN	Marteloscope	Training Material	Multiplier	Bioecon	https://informar.eu/marteloscope-sites
EN	Virtual Forest Tours	Training Material	Multiplier	Bioecon	http://sostenible.palencia.uva.es/content/virtual-forest-tours
EN	BIOES GAME - The Bioeconomy Strategy Game	Games	Multiplier	BIOES GAME	https://www.tvaweb.eu/bes/
EN	Analysis and Innovation recommendation report	Recommendation	Multiplier	Biolinx	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/D2_3_biolinx.pdf

EN	BioLinX legacy document European bio-regions: scouting and innovation recommendations	Recommendation	Multiplier	Biolinx	https://www.rewin.nl/uploads/docs/Biobased/BioLinX_longread_deliverables/BioLinX_legacy_document.pdf?u=1Ry6x
EN	Policy Recommendations BioLinX Making post project impact	Recommendation	Multiplier	Biolinx	https://fab.rewin.nl/uploads/docs/Biobased/BioLinX_longread_deliverables/BioLinX_policy_recommendations.pdf?u=1RZTfB
EN	Measuring the size of EU Bioeconomy by Input-Output Approach	Policy Brief	Multiplier	Biomonitor	https://biomonitor.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/2021-04-19_BIO_PolicyBrief_4.pdf
EN	BioMonitor Policy Scenarios for the European Bioeconomy to 2030 and 2050	Policy Brief	Multiplier	Biomonitor	https://biomonitor.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/2021-03-11_BIO_PolicyBrief-3_digital.pdf
EN	Relevance of current modelling tools for offering policy insights for the creation of a vibrant European Bioeconomy by 2030 and 2050	Policy Brief	Multiplier	Biomonitor	http://biomonitor.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/2021-03-11_BIO_PolicyBrief-2_digital.pdf
EN	BioMonitor Tools for Policy Makers and Industries: Analysing and Implementing Bioeconomy Strategies	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Biomonitor	http://biomonitor.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/2021-03-05_BIO_infopack1_digital.pdf
EN	Development of the Circular Bioeconomy: Drivers and Indicators	Publication	Multiplier	Biomonitor	http://biomonitor.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/sustainability-13-00413.pdf
EN	Friends or foes? A compatibility assessment of bioeconomy-related Sustainable Development Goals for European policy coherence	Publication	Multiplier	Biomonitor	http://biomonitor.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/Ronzon_Saniuan-2020.pdf
EN	Developments of Economic Growth and Employment in Bioeconomy Sectors across the EU	Publication	Multiplier	Biomonitor	http://biomonitor.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/sustainability-12-04507-v2.pdf
EN	Report on description of baseline scenario for EU bioeconomy and of alternative scenarios for EU's bioeconomy future	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Biomonitor	http://biomonitor.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/BioMonitor_Deliverable_6.1-May-2020-final.pdf
EN	Status quo of data collection methodologies on bioeconomy and recommendations	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Biomonitor	http://biomonitor.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/Deliverable-3.1.pdf
EN	Data and data gaps for bioeconomy drivers and indicators and their implications	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Biomonitor	http://biomonitor.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/Deliverable-2.1.pdf
EN	Opportunities and the Policy Challenges to the Circular Agri-food System	Publication	Multiplier	Biomonitor	http://biomonitor.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/Opportunities-and-the-Policy-Challenges.pdf
EN	The EU BioEconomy Contribution to Sustainable Development - Measuring the Impact	Policy Brief	Multiplier	Biomonitor	http://biomonitor.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/2019-11-BIO_policy-brief-no.1.pdf
EN	Workshop report: lessons learned and recommendations for developing clusters in the bioeconomy	Recommendation	Multiplier	Biomonitor	http://biomonitor.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/Findings-Clusters-for-Bioeconomy_Workshop_25.03.19.pdf
EN	First Stakeholder Workshop	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Biomonitor	http://biomonitor.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/Deliverable-7.2.pdf
NO	Geiter på sommerjobb gir nye inntektsmuligheter for bonden	Article	Multiplier	Bioøkonomi	https://www.landbruk.no/teknologi/geiter-pa-sommerjobb-gir-nye-inntektsmuligheter-for-bonden/
NO	Biogass fra husdyrgjødsel er vinn-vinn-vinn for norske bønder	Article	Multiplier	Bioøkonomi	https://www.landbruk.no/baerekraft/biogass-husdyrgjodsel-vinn-vinn-vinn-norske-bonder/
NO	Skogbaserte byggprodukter er god bioøkonomi	Article	Multiplier	Bioøkonomi	https://www.regjeringen.no/no/aktuelt/skogbaserte-byggprodukter-er-god-bioekonomi/id2611100/
NO	Stort potensiale for helseprodukter laget av norsk biomasse	Article	Multiplier	Bioøkonomi	https://www.landbruk.no/samvirke/stort-potensiale-for-helseprodukter-laget-av-norsk-biomasse/
EN	Collaboration opportunities	Database or repository	Supply, Multiplier	BIOPEN	https://www.biopen-project.eu/project-opportunities/
DE	Interaktive Mitmach-Ausstellung „Mission Possible – Holz -nachhaltig und wertvoll“	Project deliverable	Multiplier	BIOPROM	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/BIOPROM-detailed-description-of-exhibition-elements.pdf
DE	Spannungsbogen	Training Material	Demand	BIOPROM	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/Spannungsbogen_Bioprom3.pdf

EN	European Wood Waste Platform	Platform	Supply	BIOREG	https://www.bioreg.eu/platform/
EN	Toolbox of EU success factors	Presentation	Multiplier	BIOREG	https://www.bioreg.eu/assets/delivrables/Toolbox%20of%20EU%20success%20factors.pptx
EN	MAPPING OF EU MODEL REGIONS CASE STUDIES AND CLASSIFICATION OF WOOD	Project deliverable	Multiplier	BIOREG	https://www.bioreg.eu/assets/delivrables/BIOREG%20D2.1%20Mapping%20of%20EU%20Model%20Regions%20Case%20Studies&Classification.pdf
EN	TOOLBOX DOCUMENT OF EU SUCCESS FACTORS	Project deliverable	Supply	BIOREG	https://www.bioreg.eu/assets/delivrables/BIOREG%20D2.2%20Toolbox%20Document%20of%20EU%20Success%20Factors.pdf
EN	Wood waste management: The best practices	Good practice	Multiplier	BIOREG	https://www.bioreg.eu/assets/best-practices/BIOREG-The-Best-Practices-In-Wood-Waste-Management.pdf
DE	Altholzsammlung, -aufbereitung und -weiterverwertung: Die besten Praktiken	Good practice	Multiplier	BIOREG	https://www.bioreg.eu/assets/best-practices/BIOREG-The-Best-Practices-In-Wood-Waste-Management-in-german.pdf
EN	Success Factors of the Demonstrator Regions	Good practice	Multiplier	BIOREG	https://www.bioreg.eu/assets/best-practices/BIOREG-Success-Factors-of-The-Demonstrator-Regions.pdf
EN	Good practices in wood waste management-Austria	Good practice	Multiplier	BIOREG	https://www.bioreg.eu/assets/best-practices/BIOREG-Good-Practices-in-Wood-Waste-Management-Austria.pdf
DE	Best Practices in der Altholzwirtschaft in Österreich	Good practice	Multiplier	BIOREG	https://www.bioreg.eu/assets/best-practices/BIOREG-Good-Practices-in-Wood-Waste-Management-Austria-in-german.pdf
EN	Expert Group Workshop Identification of the good practices in waste wood management - MODEL REGION OF BADEN-WURTEMBERG	Good practice	Multiplier	BIOREG	https://www.bioreg.eu/assets/best-practices/BIOREG-Good-Practices-in-Wood-Waste-Management-Germany.pdf
EN	Expert Group Workshop Identification of the good practices in waste wood management - MODEL REGION OF LOMBARDY	Good practice	Multiplier	BIOREG	https://www.bioreg.eu/assets/best-practices/BIOREG-Good-Practices-in-Wood-Waste-Management-Italy.pdf
EN	Best practices in wood waste management UNITED KINGDOM	Good practice	Multiplier	BIOREG	https://www.bioreg.eu/assets/best-practices/BIOREG-Good-Practices-in-Wood-Waste-Management-UK.pdf
EN	LESSONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS DOCUMENT TO REGIONAL AUTHORITIES AND POLICY MAKERS	Recommendation	Multiplier	BIOREG	https://www.bioreg.eu/assets/delivrables/BIOREG%20D2.3%20Lessons%20and%20Recommendations%20document%20to%20Regional%20Authorities%20and%20Policy%20makers.pdf
EN	RECOMMENDATIONS FOR INDUSTRY STAKEHOLDERS	Recommendation	Supply	BIOREG	https://www.bioreg.eu/assets/delivrables/BIOREG%20D2.4_recommendations%20to%20industry%20stakeholders.pdf
EN	A step-by-step approach of the transition towards circular economy, case Romania	Good practice	Multiplier	BIOREGIO	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/Item-Interreg-Europe.pdf
EN	Policy Report on instruments to connect biological streams, research results and investors	Project deliverable	Multiplier	BIOREGIO	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/file_1545381951.pdf
EN	Regional road map towards circular economy	Good practice	Multiplier	BIOREGIO	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/Item-Interreg-Europe_3.pdf
EN	Smart Specialisation Platforms for Agri-Food for the Region of Central Macedonia	Good practice	Multiplier	BIOREGIO	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/Item-Interreg-Europe_2.pdf
EN	Systemic Change in National and Regional Circular Economy Transition	Policy Brief	Multiplier	BIOREGIO	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/file_1570452459.pdf
EN	Summary report on policy development	Project deliverable	Multiplier	BIOREGIO	https://www.interregeurope.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/tx_tevprojects/library/file_1569334674.docx
EN	Bio-based Circular Economy in Europe	Policy Brief	Multiplier	BIOREGIO	https://www.interregeurope.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/tx_tevprojects/library/file_1536734042.pdf
FI	Päijät-Hämeenbiokiertotalouden toimintasuunnitelma	Project deliverable	Multiplier	BIOREGIO	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/file_1559896937.pdf
EN	A NOVEL BIOREFINERY CONCEPT FOR MUSHROOM COMPOST	Fact Sheet	Multiplier	Biorescue	https://biorescue.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/1-Factsheet_Biorefinery-process_Final.pdf
EN	ULTRA RAPID BIOMASS ANALYSIS	Fact Sheet	Multiplier	Biorescue	https://biorescue.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/2-Factsheet_Rapid-biomass-analysis_Final.pdf

EN	IMPROVED ENZYMES FOR MORE EFFICIENT BIOCONVERSION	Fact Sheet	Multiplier	Biorescue	https://biorescue.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/3-Factsheet_New-Enzymatic-cocktail_Final.pdf
EN	BIO-BASED NANOCARRIERS TO TREAT PLANT DISEASES	Fact Sheet	Multiplier	Biorescue	https://biorescue.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/4-Factsheet_Nanocarriers_Final.pdf
EN	AFFORDABLE AND SUSTAINABLE BIOPESTICIDES	Fact Sheet	Multiplier	Biorescue	https://biorescue.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/5-Factsheet_Biopesticides_Final.pdf
EN	SUSTAINABILITY ASPECTS OF THE NOVEL BIORESCUE BIOREFINERY	Fact Sheet	Multiplier	Biorescue	https://biorescue.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/6-Factsheet_Sustainability_Final.pdf
EN	Case studies of national bioeconomy strategies in Finland and Germany	Case Study	Multiplier	BioSTEP	http://www.bio-step.eu/fileadmin/BioSTEP/Bio_documents/BioSTEP_D3.1_Case_studies_of_national_strategies.pdf
EN	Case studies of regional bioeconomy strategies across Europe	Case Study	Multiplier	BioSTEP	http://www.bio-step.eu/fileadmin/BioSTEP/Bio_documents/BioSTEP_D3.2_Case_studies_of_regional_strategies.pdf
EN	Good practice guidelines for stakeholder and citizen participation in bioeconomy strategies	Good practice	Multiplier	BioSTEP	http://www.bio-step.eu/fileadmin/BioSTEP/Bio_documents/BioSTEP_D3.3_Good_practice_guidelines.pdf
EN	Engaging stakeholders and citizens in the bioeconomy: Lessons learned from BioSTEP and recommendations for future research	Recommendation	Multiplier	BioSTEP	http://www.bio-step.eu/fileadmin/BioSTEP/Bio_documents/BioSTEP_D4.2_Lessons_learned_from_BioSTEP.pdf
EN	Regional bioeconomy profiles including socio-economic and environmental impacts: two case studies	Case Study	Multiplier	BioSTEP	http://www.bio-step.eu/fileadmin/BioSTEP/Bio_documents/BioSTEP_D6.1_Regional_bioeconomy_profiles.pdf
EN	Strategies for strengthened regional bioeconomies in Stara Zagora and Veneto	project deliverable	Multiplier	BioSTEP	http://www.bio-step.eu/fileadmin/BioSTEP/Bio_documents/BioSTEP_D6.2_Regional_strategies_Stara_Zagora_Veneto.pdf
EN	BioSTEP virtual exhibition	Platform	Demand	BioSTEP	http://products.bio-step.eu/
EN	Engaging Stakeholders and Citizens in the Bioeconomy BioSTEP Research Recommendations	Recommendation	Multiplier	BioSTEP	http://www.bio-step.eu/fileadmin/BioSTEP/Bio_documents/BioSTEP_Research_Recommendations_final.pdf
EN	Creating Networks for the Transition to a Bio-based and Circular Economy BioSTEP Policy Paper	Publication	Multiplier	BioSTEP	http://www.bio-step.eu/fileadmin/BioSTEP/Bio_documents/BioSTEP_Policy_Paper_final.pdf
BG	Биоикономиката в ежедневиия живот	Publication	Demand	BioSTEP	http://www.bio-step.eu/fileadmin/BioSTEP/Bio_documents/2017_Biostep_Bulgarien.pdf
IT	La bioeconomia nella vita quotidiana (PADUA)	Publication	Demand	BioSTEP	http://www.bio-step.eu/fileadmin/BioSTEP/Bio_documents/BioSTEP_Padua_low.pdf
IT	La bioeconomia nella vita quotidiana (BRESCIA)	Publication	Demand	BioSTEP	http://www.bio-step.eu/fileadmin/BioSTEP/Bio_documents/BioSTEP_Brescia_low.pdf
EN	Bioeconomy in everyday life	Publication	Demand	BioSTEP	http://www.bio-step.eu/fileadmin/BioSTEP/Bio_documents/BioSTEP_Bioeconomy-in-everyday-life_Glasgow_Exhibition-Guide.pdf
EN	Public engagement in the bioeconomy: outlining an analytical framework for BioSTEP	Publication	Multiplier	BioSTEP	http://www.bio-step.eu/fileadmin/BioSTEP/Bio_documents/BioSTEP_Working_Paper_Ribeiro_and_Millar_2015.pdf
EN	BIO-BASED READINESS SELF-ASSESSMENT TEST	Other	Supply	BIO SWITCH	https://bioswitch.eu/bioswitch-toolbox/#BIOBASED
EN	LEARNING AND AWARENESS TOOLS	Training material	Supply	BIO SWITCH	https://bioswitch.eu/bioswitch-toolbox/#learning
EN	ADOPTION TOOLS	Other	Supply	BIO SWITCH	https://bioswitch.eu/bioswitch-toolbox/#adoption
EN	CONSOLIDATION TOOLS	Other	Supply	BIO SWITCH	https://bioswitch.eu/bioswitch-toolbox/#consolidation
EN	SURVEY ON BRAND OWNERS' PERCEPTIONS WHEN SWITCHING TO BIOBASED: RISKS, NEEDS AND INCENTIVES	Project deliverable	Multiplier	BIO SWITCH	https://bioswitch.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/Survey-results.pdf
EN	THE GOOD PRACTICE CASE STUDY VAUDE SPORT GMBH & CO. KG	Case study	Supply	BIO SWITCH	https://bioswitch.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/VAUDEs-CASE-STUDY.pdf

EN	THE GOOD PRACTICE CASE STUDY BIOC BVBA	Case study	Supply	BIO SWITCH	https://bioswitch.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/BIOCQs-CASE-STUDY.pdf
EN	THE GOOD PRACTICE CASE STUDY DANTOY	Case study	Supply	BIO SWITCH	https://bioswitch.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/DANTOYs-CASE-STUDY-1_.pdf
EN	THE GOOD PRACTICE CASE STUDY OF STORA ENSO	Case study	Supply	BIO SWITCH	https://bioswitch.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/CASE-STUDY-4-STORA-ENSO-1.pdf
EN	CASE STUDY: ALHÓNDIGA LA UNIÓN, S.A.	Case study	Supply	BIO SWITCH	https://bioswitch.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/Case-Study-5-La-Union.pdf
EN	Biovoices Social media channels	Other	Multiplier	BIOVOICES	https://twitter.com/biovoices ; https://www.facebook.com/biovoices ; https://www.instagram.com/biovoices/?hl=en https://www.linkedin.com/company/biovoices/?viewAsMember=true
EN	Bio-based products collections	Other	Multiplier	BIOVOICES	-
EN	BioART Gallery	Other	Multiplier	BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices.eu/gallery/
EN	BIOVOICES Methodology to facilitate Mobilisation and Mutual Learning	Project deliverable	Multiplier	BIOVOICES	<a href="https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=111&en=key=53491c2ff4014310b65cc09d617fc
c34">https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=111&en=key=53491c2ff4014310b65cc09d617fc c34
EN	BIOVOICES book for kids	Publication	Multiplier	BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices.eu/book/concept/
EN	Circular bioeconomy stories	Video	Multiplier	BIOVOICES	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCqlonia8vTITpvir7XxX7FA/videos
EN	The BIOArt Gallery Booklet	Publication	Multiplier	BIOVOICES	<a href="https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=118&en=key=48d393b4e718a6ea02718f0c8b31
476a">https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=118&en=key=48d393b4e718a6ea02718f0c8b31 476a
EN	BIOVOICES Platform	Platform	Supply	BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices-platform.eu/
EN	What are bio-based products?	Other	Supply	BIOVOICES	<a href="https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=129&en=key=2ce113307995affe18121f94cc44b
d7e">https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=129&en=key=2ce113307995affe18121f94cc44b d7e
EN	What is bioeconomy?	Other	Supply	BIOVOICES	<a href="https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=130&en=key=c0f4a5ab287109374fad099794bd
d665">https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=130&en=key=c0f4a5ab287109374fad099794bd d665
EN	What is the relation between bioeconomy and bio- based economy?	Other	Supply	BIOVOICES	<a href="https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=137&en=key=9a8f4c7a2db73e9def05432b4203
7bc6">https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=137&en=key=9a8f4c7a2db73e9def05432b4203 7bc6
EN	What is biomass?	Other	Supply	BIOVOICES	<a href="https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=128&en=key=b0d4adb0a29eeda9e4025f73d6b3
cc1e">https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=128&en=key=b0d4adb0a29eeda9e4025f73d6b3 cc1e
EN	Is all biomass subject to the same regulation?	Other	Supply	BIOVOICES	<a href="https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=140&en=key=3d3a7ec0480c312ffdf0b740b919a
c36">https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=140&en=key=3d3a7ec0480c312ffdf0b740b919a c36
EN	Is biomass only for bioenergy?	Other	Supply	BIOVOICES	<a href="https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=139&en=key=10aaeafa67af27a85ac8b54d4f8a8
e6c">https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=139&en=key=10aaeafa67af27a85ac8b54d4f8a8 e6c
EN	What is a value chain?	Other	Supply	BIOVOICES	<a href="https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=142&en=key=54be6578a0dd6159e80af1caf70bf
d84">https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=142&en=key=54be6578a0dd6159e80af1caf70bf d84
EN	What is a cross-sector interconnection?	Other	Supply	BIOVOICES	<a href="https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=143&en=key=56cd9de3f17f3b89bb5f63ef298f1
5e">https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=143&en=key=56cd9de3f17f3b89bb5f63ef298f1 5e
EN	What is a bio-based material?	Other	Supply	BIOVOICES	<a href="https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=144&en=key=528380d56555a23b9ea953fa8468
0b05">https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=144&en=key=528380d56555a23b9ea953fa8468 0b05
EN	Is the bioeconomy a promising sector?	Other	Supply	BIOVOICES	<a href="https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=138&en=key=cf099b4beaab52c37a217310ea82
5e83">https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=138&en=key=cf099b4beaab52c37a217310ea82 5e83
EN	What does home compostable mean?	Other	Supply	BIOVOICES	<a href="https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=136&en=key=676b719a56fce35609e4b788f1acf
d5b">https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=136&en=key=676b719a56fce35609e4b788f1acf d5b
EN	What does the label OK BIOBASED mean?	Other	Supply	BIOVOICES	<a href="https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=135&en=key=08c4e237fcc37aa578c3f0f3dc072
6df">https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=135&en=key=08c4e237fcc37aa578c3f0f3dc072 6df
EN	What does biodegradable really mean?	Other	Supply	BIOVOICES	<a href="https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=134&en=key=ef9d2edcb3ce3e38bbebd8556fd5
84ce">https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=134&en=key=ef9d2edcb3ce3e38bbebd8556fd5 84ce
EN	Does bio-based mean biodegradable?	Other	Supply	BIOVOICES	<a href="https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=133&en=key=d4e8f465fdb07e992e490a095445
bd88">https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=133&en=key=d4e8f465fdb07e992e490a095445 bd88
EN	Does biodegradable mean bio-based?	Other	Supply	BIOVOICES	<a href="https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=132&en=key=a8175104856582c7eae66fac808
abca">https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=132&en=key=a8175104856582c7eae66fac808 abca

EN	Are bioplastics necessarily biodegradable?	Other	Supply	BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=131&f=en&key=6f5ee4ba1886676360e573ac8c8f0a2c
EN	What is bioplastic?	Other	Supply	BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=127&f=en&key=f58f939db4253fd5c8d09a34fda3f0d0
EN	What is biofuel?	Other	Supply	BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=126&f=en&key=96b0c0db3a53d2f962668cea06bb2f0f
EN	What are bio-based chemicals?	Other	Supply	BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=125&f=en&key=0d8a65233fbf415e4f27e47b2d2f0464
EN	What is wood-based fashion?	Other	Supply	BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=124&f=en&key=f0b2d863002d2d8d3929e1790e01f7bce
EN	Synthesis of market perspectives to develop bio-based value chains	Project deliverable	Multiplier	BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=5&f=en&key=d4d623ecfaf04313fb52c36f48bccf2
EN	Interviews Data Analysis Identification of Stakeholders' Interests and Motivations	Project deliverable	Multiplier	BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=34&f=en&key=6b75b921fe9a263e48ce727aadd68bd8a
EN	Mapping bio-based products (applications) based on stakeholders' interests	Project deliverable	Multiplier	BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=35&f=en&key=3693dd48b0a5d4d038ae13697f153d8f
EN	Guide for Mobilisation and Mutual Learning workshops	Project deliverable	Multiplier	BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=39&f=en&key=7d8bc103e1b7d3bc1748c5a29c052074
EN	Stakeholders' classification	Project deliverable	Multiplier	BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=6&f=en&key=83d68db382d34c23d2d12dc6164aad8a
EN	Focus group report	Project deliverable	Multiplier	BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=43&f=en&key=f0afe35bef6d86abe21d37832cd0cc13
EN	BIOVoices multistakeholder on-line social platform: v2.0	Project deliverable	Multiplier	BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=233&f=en&key=abb170f8488f62fa5ad060c5c1b80b61
EN	Population of the BIOVoices multi-stakeholder on-line platform with contents Report (first version)	Project deliverable	Multiplier	BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=44&f=en&key=04b499009794d8151d7a2ae97167cc6
EN	Animation of the Multi Stakeholders Platform Report	Project deliverable	Multiplier	BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=232&f=en&key=cab588f44a9b15faf90024b1ab04a19a
EN	The BIOVOICES app	Project deliverable	Multiplier	BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=231&f=en&key=7e002cc39e2fbf2dc730aa9818faf424
EN	Social Media innovative engagement and animation Report: first version	Project deliverable	Multiplier	BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=230&f=en&key=f78c441e0db65683882f6140ccff15df
EN	Report on European, National and Regional MML events	Project deliverable	Multiplier	BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=228&f=en&key=b4ed2e36a10fac43c53916a350772a0b
EN	BIOVOICES Action Plan and Stakeholder-Oriented Policy Briefs	Project deliverable	Multiplier	BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=227&f=en&key=df652b832217462bb96eb368b057ad26
EN	The circular economy offers bio-based sectors a licence to produce	Publication	Multiplier	BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=225&f=en&key=593e336863d2c416b9ba47a5b8a4a9ba
NL	Meer doen met natuurlijke isolatiematerialen	Publication	Multiplier	BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=224&f=en&key=36e2240582e3ac0b060a375482689aec
NL	Biobased Bouwen	Publication	Supply	BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=223&f=en&key=c7e79acf00465523242d921b075474a4
EN	Bioeconomy Transformation Strategies Worldwide Require Stronger Focus on Entrepreneurship	Publication	Multiplier	BIOVOICES	https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/12/7/2911/pdf
EN	BIOVOICES POLICY BRIEF FOR THE RESEARCH SECTOR	Policy brief	Multiplier	BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=215&f=en&key=9d8d10826bc2eae3a67b03e47dac443e
EN	BIOVOICES POLICY BRIEF FOR POLICYMAKERS	Policy brief	Multiplier	BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=214&f=en&key=67b7d20a71baad2f0b39dee5a9e78fa6

EN	BIOVOICES POLICY BRIEF FOR CIVIL SOCIETY	Policy brief	Multiplier	BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=213&l=en&key=5bffc10dc703758db89f2a396c80501a
EN	BIOVOICES POLICY BRIEF FOR THE BUSINESS SECTOR	Policy brief	Supply	BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=212&l=en&key=9c7c53c1fd312601eda39432054c5d84
EN	BIOVOICES ACTION PLAN FOR CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT	Recommendation	Multiplier	BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices.eu/download.php?f=216&l=en&key=4f48492885b3ba5ffc399495d8940ab0
EN	The bioeconomy in our everyday lives - BIOWAYS video	Video	Demand	BIOWAYS	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ir3MqOSmvLg
EN	BIO...What? the bioeconomy game	Games	Demand	BIOWAYS	https://www.fvaweb.eu/biowhat/
EN	BIOChallenge	Games	Demand	BIOWAYS	https://www.fvaweb.eu/biochallenge/
EN	Public perception of bio-based products – societal needs and concerns (updated version)	Project deliverable	Multiplier	BIOWAYS	https://www.bioways.eu/download.php?f=307&l=en&key=f1d76bf7f2ae06b3ee3d4372a896d977
EN	Bio-based products and applications potential	Project deliverable	Multiplier	BIOWAYS	https://www.bioways.eu/download.php?f=150&l=en&key=441a4e6a27f83a8e828b802c37adc6e1
EN	List of relevant initiatives supporting the development and uptake of bio-based products at European and regional level	Project deliverable	Multiplier	BIOWAYS	https://www.bioways.eu/download.php?f=221&l=en&key=b4a1c5e88e7e5a81045f645879d03dda
EN	Applications Factsheets	Fact sheet	Supply	BIOWAYS	https://www.bioways.eu/bio-learn/applications-factsheets/
EN	Biolubricants	Fact sheet	Multiplier	BIOWAYS	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1HQY4w2R04iXtQis20YAMK7JOLiXchTJ/view
EN	Bio-economy and Bio-based products	Fact sheet	Multiplier	BIOWAYS	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Ez-gQ2ZK6Nnd-fUW9AAht1O7Xt4fiSg9/view
EN	Biosurfactants	Fact sheet	Multiplier	BIOWAYS	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1pV2wKRcdW1MTZamReavmhSAM-sYHtmAG/view
EN	Biochemicals	Fact sheet	Multiplier	BIOWAYS	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1RBV1oqvcWp97NnmAZtfnrLalLBy0qir/view
EN	Biofuels	Fact sheet	Multiplier	BIOWAYS	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1R2UJQmrw7VM0ohwLiCINmX2wEqXi2xuW/view
EN	Bioenergy	Fact sheet	Multiplier	BIOWAYS	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1FWnA0uk3lr2i2rC53JN6jPi8eCBQeAJ0/view
EN	Food Ingredients and Feed	Fact sheet	Multiplier	BIOWAYS	https://drive.google.com/file/d/11-hNsXqJlYHusj0AbiCC92vedXzhTOLc/view
EN	Bio-based Plastics	Fact sheet	Multiplier	BIOWAYS	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1TfmjGJUZOBT0TqOkLi3T1qdBu8SHkpl/view
EN	What is Bioeconomy?	Presentation	Demand	BIOWAYS	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/Educational_multimedia_presentations-1.pdf
EN	BIOWAYS 60' Science videos - From bio-based research to Bio-based products	Video	Demand	BIOWAYS	https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLk-gaYFMdulFS0FPU7V1Zvpk-dAuPfMe
ES	La bioeconomía en nuestra vida diaria	Video	Demand	BIOWAYS	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XO7voVaXUcw
GR	Η βιοοικονομία στην καθημερινή μας ζωή	Video	Demand	BIOWAYS	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pTLs5OiiYPk
IT	La bioeconomia nella vita di tutti i giorni	Video	Demand	BIOWAYS	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mTOJi7uLIAU
PT	A bio economia no nosso dia-a-dia	Video	Demand	BIOWAYS	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=L932WlCy_-4
SK	Biohospodárstvo v našom každonennom živote	Video	Demand	BIOWAYS	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=M3PSYiXR0h4
ET	Biomajandus meie igapäevaelus	Video	Demand	BIOWAYS	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HUK0RN_7SaY
EN	Environmental Sustainability Assessment of Bioeconomy Products and Processes –Progress Report 1	Publication	Multiplier	BISO	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/lb-na-27356-en-n.pdf
EN	METHODOLOGY FOR ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT IN THE FRAMEWORK OF BIOECONOMY OBSERVATORY	Publication	Multiplier	BISO	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/JRC88527_BISO-Env-Sust-Methodology_140818.pdf
EN	How poop will change the world	Training material	Multiplier	BLOOM	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/BLOOM-LS-TEAM4-How-to-change-online.pdf
EN	Implementation of learning scenario Nr 3	video	Multiplier	BLOOM	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6xucTUujs1Q
EN	Building a new environmental future	Training material	Multiplier	BLOOM	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/BLOOM-LS-TEAM3-Building-online.pdf
EN	Bioeconomy for a Sustainable Future	Training material	Multiplier	BLOOM	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/BLOOM-SoI-Semih-Esendemir.pdf

EN	Don't waste your waste! -Raising bioeconomy awareness	Training material	Multiplier	BLOOM	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/BLOOM-LS-compet-Dont-waste-your-waste.pdf
EN	My kitchen without food waste	Training material	Multiplier	BLOOM	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/BLOOM-SoA-Marina-Stanojlovic.pdf
EN	BLOOM Quiz on bioeconomy	Games	Multiplier	BLOOM	http://quiz.bloom-bioeconomy.eu/
FI	BLOOM Quiz on bioeconomy	Games	Multiplier	BLOOM	http://fi.quiz.bloom-bioeconomy.eu/
DE	BLOOM Quiz on bioeconomy	Games	Multiplier	BLOOM	http://de.quiz.bloom-bioeconomy.eu/
ES	BLOOM Quiz on bioeconomy	Games	Multiplier	BLOOM	http://es.quiz.bloom-bioeconomy.eu/
EN	BLOOM Bioeconomy Infographic	Presentation	Demand	BLOOM	https://prezi.com/view/cDUtdrT0P5xqhiFUrA8g/
EN	Outreach & Engagement Guidebook	Publication	Multiplier	BLOOM	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/BLOOM-Outreach-Engagement-Guidebook.pdf
EN	Co-creation Guidebook	Publication	Multiplier	BLOOM	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/BLOOM-Co-creation-Guidebook.pdf
PL-ES-SV-NL-FI-EN-DE	The BLOOM School Box	Training material	Multiplier	BLOOM	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/schoolnetwork/schoolbox/
EN	Boosting Bioeconomy Knowledge in Schools	Training material	Multiplier	BLOOM	https://www.europeanschoolnetacademy.eu/courses/course-v1:BLOOM+BoostBioec+2019/about
EN	What is the Bioeconomy?	Fact sheet	Multiplier	BLOOM	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/BLOOM-Factsheet-What-is-the-Bioeconomy.pdf
EN	Bioeconomy Questions and Answers	Other	Multiplier	BLOOM	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/bioeconomy-questions-and-answers/
EN	Key Messages	Presentation	Multiplier	BLOOM	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/key-messages/
ES	Biomasa para la economía circular	Publication	Multiplier	BLOOM	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/Biomasa-para-la-economia-circular-versie-site.pdf
EN	A journey to the bioeconomy future! with a suitcase packed with great products	Publication	Demand	BLOOM	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/Bioeconomy-suitcase-leaflet.pdf
EN	Biobased Plastics 2020	Publication	Multiplier	BLOOM	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/Bioplastics-English-versie-site.pdf
EN	Biomass for the Circular Economy - Everything you wanted to know about biomass but were afraid to ask	Publication	Multiplier	BLOOM	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Biomass-for-the-circular-economy-EN-site.pdf
EN	Framework of concepts	Presentation	Multiplier	BLOOM	https://prezi.com/view/aJydzYhkr89QPY6ExqG/
DE	Neuer Baukasten für INNOVATIONEN	Article	Multiplier	BLOOM	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/FURCHE_Bioökonomie_gesamt.pdf
EN	BLOOM Podcasts	Other	Multiplier	BLOOM	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/podcasts/
EN	BLOOM Videos	Video	Demand	BLOOM	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/videos/
EN	How to promote education, training and skills across the bioeconomy	Article	Multiplier	BLOOM	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/2019/10/31/promote-education-training-skills-across-bioeconomy/
EN	Compilation of stakeholder targeted materials	Database or repository	Multiplier	BLOOM	https://bloom-bioeconomy.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/D1.3-Compilation-of-stakeholder-targeted-materials.pdf
EN	Bioeconomy Game	Games	demand	Campus des Métiers et des Qualifications d'excellence BioEco Academy	https://games.focusgames.co.uk/bioeconomy_game/game/
EN	Jobs and growth GENERATED BY INDUSTRIAL BIOTECHNOLOGY IN EUROPE	Infographics	Multiplier	Campus des Métiers et des Qualifications d'excellence BioEco Academy	https://www.univ-reims.fr/cm9/media-files/21114/emploi-et-croissance-info.pdf
FR	La bioéconomie, une approche nouvelle pour des solutions durables	Presentation	Multiplier	Campus des Métiers et des Qualifications d'excellence BioEco Academy	https://www.dailymotion.com/video/x6srdf
FR	La Bioéconomie durable	Infographics	Multiplier	Campus des Métiers et des Qualifications d'excellence BioEco Academy	http://multimedia.ademe.fr/infographies/infographie_bioeconomie/

FR	UNE STRATÉGIE BIOÉCONOMIE POUR LA FRANCE	Publication	Multiplier	Campus des Métiers et des Qualifications d'excellence BioEco Academy	https://www.univ-reims.fr/aebb/media-files/18806/bioeconomie-2018-v2-hd.pdf
EN	European Bioeconomy in Figures2008 –2016	Publication	Multiplier	Campus des Métiers et des Qualifications d'excellence BioEco Academy	https://www.univ-reims.fr/cmqa/media-files/21118/european-bioeconomy-in-figures-2008-2016_0.pdf
FR	Dynamiques de l'emploi dans les filières bioéconomiques	Publication	Multiplier	Campus des Métiers et des Qualifications d'excellence BioEco Academy	https://www.vie-publique.fr/sites/default/files/rapport/pdf/164000372.pdf
EN	JOBS AND GROWTH generated by induSTrial biotechnology in europe	Publication	Multiplier	Campus des Métiers et des Qualifications d'excellence BioEco Academy	https://www.univ-reims.fr/cmqa/media-files/21108/full-version-ib-jobs-and-growth-study_0.pdf
EN	CommBeBiz Knowledge Portal	Database or repository	Multiplier	CommBeBiz	https://commbebiz.eu/?page=1729
EN	BeBizBlueprint Insights on the Road to Innovation Maximising researcher impact through communications and business support	Publication	Multiplier	CommBeBiz	https://ebn.eu/sharedResources/projects/CommBeBiz/180223%20CBB%20Blueprint.pdf
EN	Bioeconomy Innovation	Other	Multiplier	CommBeBiz	https://ebn.eu/sharedResources/projects/CommBeBiz/magazine/CommBeBiz%20Magazine%202017-2018%20HiRes.pdf
EN	CommBeBiz Testinar - What biotech can do to help us live more sustainably	Training material	Multiplier	CommBeBiz	https://commbebiz.eu/?post=commbebiz-testinar-what-biotech-can-do-to-help-us-live-more-sustainably
EN	Top Tips on Short Videos for Bioeconomy Researchers	project deliverable	Multiplier	CommBeBiz	https://ebn.eu/sharedResources/users/5006/171218%20-%20CBB%20ESC%20Top%20Tips%20on%20Video.pdf
EN	Top Tips - Image ining for Scientific Photography	Video	Multiplier	CommBeBiz	https://commbebiz.eu/?post=top-tips-image-ining-for-scientific-photography
EN	100+ Biobased Products for Biobased Living	Video	Multiplier	CommBeBiz	https://commbebiz.eu/?post=webinar-100-biobased-products-for-biobased-living-2
EN	Market partner research for bioeconomy researchers	Video	Multiplier	CommBeBiz	https://commbebiz.eu/?post=market-partner-research-for-bioeconomy-researchers-
EN	Webinar Responsible Research and Innovation RRI in the Bioeconomy	Video	Multiplier	CommBeBiz	https://commbebiz.eu/?post=webinar-responsible-research-and-innovation-rri-in-the-bioeconomy-
EN	Bioeconomy goes digital a testinar on Smart Agri Smart Food Solutions	Training material	Multiplier	CommBeBiz	https://commbebiz.eu/?post=bioeconomy-goes-digital-a-testinar-on-smart-agri-smart-food-solutions-
EN	Business plan writing for bioeconomy researchers	Video	Multiplier	CommBeBiz	https://commbebiz.eu/?post=business-plan-writing-for-bioeconomy-researchers-
EN	Bioplastics - the next sustainability challenge in a circular economy	Video	Multiplier	CommBeBiz	https://commbebiz.eu/?post=bioplastics-the-next-sustainability-challenge-in-a-circular-economy-
EN	Webinar - Open Science and Data Sharing	Video	Multiplier	CommBeBiz	https://commbebiz.eu/?post=webinar-open-science-and-data-sharing
EN	CommBeBiz Webinar One - Testinar on forestry based industries	Training material	Multiplier	CommBeBiz	https://commbebiz.eu/?post=commbebiz-webinar-one-testinar-on-forestry-based-industries--1
EN	CommBeBiz Marine Testinar - Unlocking the blue potential	Training material	Multiplier	CommBeBiz	https://commbebiz.eu/?post=commbebiz-marine-testinar-unlocking-the-blue-potential-1
EN	CommBeBiz Webinar - Intellectual Property Rights in the bioeconomy	Video	Multiplier	CommBeBiz	https://commbebiz.eu/?post=commbebiz-webinar-intellectual-property-rights-in-the-bioeconomy-
EN	CommBeBiz Webinar - Circular Economy – Strategies for organizations in the bioeconomy	Video	Multiplier	CommBeBiz	https://commbebiz.eu/?post=commbebiz-webinar-circular-economy-strategies-for-organizations-in-the-bioeconomy
EN	CommBeBiz Webinar on Science Journalism	Video	Multiplier	CommBeBiz	https://commbebiz.eu/?post=commbebiz-webinar-on-science-journalism
EN	CommBeBiz Webinar on Climate Change	Video	Multiplier	CommBeBiz	https://commbebiz.eu/?post=commbebiz-webinar-on-climate-change-
EN	CommBeBiz Webinar on Research Policy	Video	Multiplier	CommBeBiz	https://commbebiz.eu/?post=commbebiz-webinar-on-research-policy
EN	CommBeBiz Webinar 6 - Social Innovation in the Bioeconomy	Video	Multiplier	CommBeBiz	https://commbebiz.eu/?post=commbebiz-webinar-6-social-innovation-in-the-bioeconomy
EN	CommBeBiz Testinar Two - Food Science and Technologies	Training material	Multiplier	CommBeBiz	https://commbebiz.eu/?post=commbebiz-testinar-two-food-science-and-technologies

EN	CommBeBiz Webinar One - Testinar on forestry based industries	Training material	Multiplier	CommBeBiz	https://commbebiz.eu/?post=commbebiz-webinar-one-testinar-on-forestry-based-industries
EN	CommBeBiz: Bioeconomy to Business	Video	Multiplier	CommBeBiz	https://commbebiz.eu/?post=commbebiz-bioeconomy-to-business
EN	The EU Guide to Science Communication	Video	Multiplier	CommBeBiz	https://commbebiz.eu/?post=the-eu-guide-to-science-communication-
EN	BUILDING THE BIOECONOMY CREATING IMPACT THROUGH COMMUNICATION	Publication	Multiplier	CommFABNet	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/Commfabnet-final-publication.pdf
EN-DE-DA-FR-IT-ES	Know your food	Training material	Multiplier	CommFABNet	http://commnet.eu/01_About_CommNet/Commnet_Community/Education/FAB_Toolkit/Year2/Know-Your-Food.ki
EN	Catalogue of descriptive factsheets of all European case studies	Case study	Multiplier	CONSOLE	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1L2KJvuS5NmR2hQ2UJ2Ja3X_akaQ4Lkix/view
EN	Proposal for Alignment of National & EU Funding Schemes	project deliverable	Multiplier	DanuBioValNet	http://www.interreg-danube.eu/uploads/media/approved_project_output/0001/34/1cec9bb638e988eea3e62816e389ac93fb6fccf.pdf
EN	Joint Strategy for Bio-Based Industry Cluster Policy	project deliverable	Multiplier	DanuBioValNet	http://www.interreg-danube.eu/uploads/media/approved_project_output/0001/33/a397b5b1df812eb8f1670245beaa3800e7fd42.pdf
EN	Cluster Tool Box „New Cluster Services to support SMEs in bio-based industries“	project deliverable	Multiplier	DanuBioValNet	http://www.interreg-danube.eu/uploads/media/approved_project_output/0001/32/92be3e66154430dbe1e68b16d5fe324bd9068316.pdf
EN	The BioBased Status in the Danube Region	project deliverable	Multiplier	DanuBioValNet	http://www.interreg-danube.eu/uploads/media/approved_project_output/0001/25/259396cc13270d6c3f73d1693967b78a53003153.pdf
EN	EBU OPINION PAPER: The Bioeconomy and the Green Deal	Publication	Multiplier	EBU	https://european-bioeconomy-university.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/EBU-opinion-paper_GreenDeal_final.pdf
EN	Report on specialized Forum on Waste and Circular Economy	project deliverable	Multiplier	EMBRACED	https://embraced.eu/repository/EMBRACED_D7.5_Report-on-specialized-Forum-DEF.pdf
EN	Policy recommendation to overcome legislative barriers for the recovery of AHP waste as secondary raw material	Recommendation	Multiplier	EMBRACED	https://embraced.eu/repository/EMBRACED_D6.1_Legislative-barriers_DEF.pdf
EN	Why the future of consumption is circular	Article	Multiplier	EMBRACED	https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2018/01/future-consumption-circular-economy-sustainable
EN	D3.8 Best Practice Sheet in the EIP-AGRI format	Project deliverable	Supply	Enabling	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/D3.8_ENABLING_BestPracticeSheetintheEIP-AGRIformat.pdf
EN	D2.1 Information matrix for the provision of data on availability of resources and identification of industrial processes	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Enabling	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/D2.1_Informationmatrixfortheprovisionofdataonavailabilityofresources.pdf
EN	Innovation Watch	Platform	Multiplier	Enabling	https://www.enabling-project.com/innovation-watch
EN	Report on the main R&D needs, drivers and trends in forest raw material production, sourcing and availability	Project deliverable	Multiplier	ERIFORE	http://static.erifore.eu/content/uploads/2016/12/ERIFORE-D1.4-20161101_FCBA.pdf
EN	Report on the main R&D needs, drivers and trends in primary processing	Project deliverable	Multiplier	ERIFORE	http://static.erifore.eu/content/uploads/2016/12/ERIFORE_D2.3_Tecnalia_30092016.pdf
EN	Report on the main R&D needs, drivers and trends in secondary processing	Project deliverable	Multiplier	ERIFORE	http://static.erifore.eu/content/uploads/2016/12/ERIFORE-D3-3_VTT_30092016.pdf
EN	Report on the main R&D needs, drivers and trends in downstream processing	Project deliverable	Multiplier	ERIFORE	http://static.erifore.eu/content/uploads/2016/12/ERIFORE_D4.3_KTH30092016.pdf
EN	Research infrastructure capability check and bottleneck analysis	Project deliverable	Multiplier	ERIFORE	http://static.erifore.eu/content/uploads/2016/12/ERIFORE_D5.1_30112016_WKP.pdf

EN	List of significant emerging concepts and evaluation of infrastructure capabilities to meet forthcoming plans	Project deliverable	Multiplier	ERIFORE	http://static.erifore.eu/content/uploads/2017/05/ERIFORE_5.2_VTT_20170228.pdf
EN	Case studies and preliminary business models	Case Study	Supply	ERIFORE	http://static.erifore.eu/content/uploads/2017/08/D5.3_20172006_RISE.pdf
EN	Analysis and report on industry mapping and stakeholder interviews	Project deliverable	Multiplier	ERIFORE	http://static.erifore.eu/content/uploads/2017/05/20170228_ERIFORE_5.4_WoodKplus.pdf
EN	Report on the educational and training use of the infrastructure network	Project deliverable	Multiplier	ERIFORE	http://static.erifore.eu/content/uploads/2017/08/ERIFORE-D7.4-03052017_AALTO.pdf
EN	Success stories	Database or repository	Multiplier	EU Research & Innovation	https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/projects/success-stories
EN	Bio-based products From idea to market "15 EU success stories"	Publication	Supply	EU Research & Innovation	https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/23ab58e0-3011-11e9-8d04-01aa75ed71a1
EN	The bioeconomy starts here!	video	Multiplier	EU Science & Innovation	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2xvXkOMRTs4
EN	A new bioeconomy for a sustainable Europe	Video	Multiplier	EU Science & Innovation	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RfRN_hHeIKk
EN	The European Fruit Network (EUFRUIT) - Knowledge Platform	Database or repository	Multiplier	EUFRUIT	https://kp.eufrin.eu/
EN	Toolkits and guidelines	Database or repository	Multiplier	European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform	https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/en/toolkits-guidelines
EN	Good Practices	Database or repository	Supply	European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform	https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/good-practices
EN	Strategies	Database or repository	Multiplier	European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform	https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/strategies
EN	Knowledge	Database or repository	Multiplier	European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform	https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/knowledge
EN	European Circular Economy Networks / Platforms	Database or repository	Multiplier	European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform	https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/dialogue/existing-eu-platforms
EN	Education	Database or repository	Multiplier	European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform	https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/en/education
EN	European Network for Rural Development Projects & Practice	Database or repository	Multiplier	European Network for Rural Development	https://enrd.ec.europa.eu/projects-practice_en
EN	LAG Database	Database or repository	Multiplier	European Network for Rural Development	https://enrd.ec.europa.eu/leader-clld/laq-database_en
EN	LEADER Resources	Platform	Multiplier	European Network for Rural Development	https://enrd.ec.europa.eu/leader-clld/leader-resources_en
EN	NRN Toolkit	Platform	Multiplier	European Network for Rural Development	https://enrd.ec.europa.eu/networking/nrn-toolkit_en
EN	Long Term Rural Vision Portal	Platform	Multiplier	European Network for Rural Development	https://enrd.ec.europa.eu/enrd-thematic-work/long-term-rural-vision/long-term-rural-vision-portal_en
EN	Common Agricultural Policy post-2020	Platform	Multiplier	European Network for Rural Development	https://enrd.ec.europa.eu/policy-in-action/common-agricultural-policy-post-2020_en
EN	Rural Bioeconomy Portal	Platform	Multiplier	European Network for Rural Development	https://enrd.ec.europa.eu/greening-rural-economy/bioeconomy/rural-bioeconomy-portal_en
EN	Smart Villages Portal	Platform	Multiplier	European Network for Rural Development	https://enrd.ec.europa.eu/smart-and-competitive-rural-areas/smart-villages/smart-villages-portal_en
EN	Social Inclusion	Platform	Multiplier	European Network for Rural Development	https://enrd.ec.europa.eu/enrd-thematic-work/social-inclusion_en
EN	European Network for Rural Development Publications	Database or repository	Multiplier	European Network for Rural Development	https://enrd.ec.europa.eu/publications/search_en
EN	European Network for Rural Development Evaluation Publications	Database or repository	Multiplier	European Network for Rural Development	https://enrd.ec.europa.eu/evaluation/publications_en

EN	Trainings	Training Material	Multiplier	FASTER	https://faster-h2020.eu/index.php/research-excellence-trainings/
EN	E-learning Platform	Platform	Multiplier	FASTER	https://faster-h2020.eu/index.php/e-learning-platform/
EN	Knowledge Hub	Platform	Multiplier	FASTER	https://faster-h2020.eu/index.php/knowledge-hub/
EN	Fertimanure Circular Economy Strategy	Other	Supply	Fertimanure	https://www.fertimanure.eu/en/the-project-s-response
EN	Curricula/Courses database	Database or repository	Demand	Fields	http://www.erasmus-fields.eu/management/?q=curricula-courses-database%20
EN	Project database	Database or repository	Supply	Fields	http://www.erasmus-fields.eu/management/?q=project-database
EN	Best practices database	Database or repository	Supply, Multiplier	Fields	http://www.erasmus-fields.eu/management/?q=best-practices-database
EN	Future-Proofing our Food systems through Research and Innovation	Publication	Multiplier	Fit4Food2030	https://fit4food2030.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/02/food2030-future-proofing-our-food-systems.pdf
EN	Harnessing Research and Innovation for FOOD 2030: A science policy dialogue	Publication	Multiplier	Fit4Food2030	https://fit4food2030.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/02/food2030_report_conference_2017.pdf
EN	European Research & Innovation for Food & Nutrition Security	Publication	Multiplier	Fit4Food2030	https://fit4food2030.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/KI0716013ENN.en_.pdf
EN	A SYSTEMS APPROACH TO RESEARCH AND INNOVATION FOR FOOD SYSTEM TRANSFORMATION	Policy Brief	Multiplier	Fit4Food2030	https://fit4food2030.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/FIT4FOOD2030-A-Systems-Approach-to-Research-and-Innovation-for-Food-System-Transformation-Policy-Brief.pdf
EN	KEY RESEARCH AND INNOVATION QUESTIONS ON ENGAGING CONSUMERS IN THE DELIVERY OF FOOD 2030	Policy Brief	Multiplier	Fit4Food2030	https://fit4food2030.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/FIT4FOOD2030-Research-and-Innovation-supporting-the-Farm-to-Fork-Strategy-of-the-European-Commission-Policy-Brief.pdf
EN	GOVERNANCE OF RESEARCH TO ACCELERATE INNOVATION, DELIVER TRANSFORMATION AND DEMONSTRATE FLEXIBILITY AT THE TIME OF SHOCKS	Policy Brief	Multiplier	Fit4Food2030	https://fit4food2030.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/12/FIT4FOOD2030_-_Policy-Brief-4_EU-TT_final.pdf
EN	CULTIVATING BREAKTHROUGHS FOR A HEALTHIER AND MORE SUSTAINABLE FOOD SYSTEM	Recommendation	Multiplier	Fit4Food2030	https://fit4food2030.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/onepager-F4F-Web.pdf
EN	Co-designing educational modules	Training Material	Multiplier	Fit4Food2030	https://knowledgehub.fit4food2030.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/FIT4FOOD2030_Tool_Co-designingEduModules.pdf
EN	Citizen consultation on food system transformation	Training Material	Multiplier	Fit4Food2030	https://knowledgehub.fit4food2030.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/FIT4FOOD2030_Tool_CitizenConsultationWorkshop-1.pdf
EN	Designing multi-stakeholder events	Training Material	Multiplier	Fit4Food2031	https://knowledgehub.fit4food2030.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/FIT4FOOD2030_Tool_DesigningMS_Events-1.pdf
EN	Guideline for the design and implementation of joint "industrial master" curricula in FS&T/E	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Food-STA	https://www.food-sta.eu/sites/default/files/wp_deliverables/D4.7.pdf
EN	Report on identification of Good Practices in Innovation in teaching and learning	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Food-STA	https://www.food-sta.eu/sites/default/files/wp_deliverables/D5.1.pdf
EN	ISEKI-Food E-learning	Database or repository	Demand, Multiplier	Food-STA	https://moodle.iseki-food.net/
EN	Digital Library for the Food Sector	Database or repository	Demand, Multiplier	Food-STA	https://db.iseki-food.net/digital-library/output
EN	Database on Experts in the Food Sector	Database or repository	Multiplier	Food-STA	https://db.iseki-food.net/database/expert
EN	Search Training Activities	Database or repository	Demand	Food-STA	https://www.foodcareers.eu/search-training-activities
EN	EUROPEAN BIOBASED KNOWLEDGE NETWORK	Database or repository	Demand, Supply, Multiplier	GBO	https://biobasednetwork.eu/home/

NL	De professional van de toekomst in de Biobased Economy	Project deliverable	Multiplier	GBO	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/GBO-Marktconsultatie.pdf
NL	Rapportage Trainings- en Research-faciliteiten	Project deliverable	Multiplier	GBO	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/GBO-Trainings-en-Researchfaciliteiten.pdf
EN	Report on Market Studies	Project deliverable	Supply, Multiplier	Glaukos	https://glaukos.fvaweb.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Glaukos-Report-on-market-studies_for-publication.pdf
EN	Regional Stakeholder Reports	project deliverable	Multiplier	GoDanuBio	http://www.interreg-danube.eu/uploads/media/approved_project_output/0001/44/ccf91f7e139fd8bf461f20a23ab5c7ea5d0e2ee.zip
EN	Capitalisation of projects and macroregional documents - Regional reports	project deliverable	Multiplier	GoDanuBio	http://www.interreg-danube.eu/uploads/media/approved_project_output/0001/43/61f5748721ae2a40603172f1ec2d475c855f63ae.zip
EN	OECD- REALISING THE CIRCULAR BIOECONOMY	Publication	Multiplier	Greenchemistry Lombardia	https://www.chimicaverdelombardia.it/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/Report-OECD-Realising-the-circular-bioeconomy.pdf
EN	"Functional proteins from vegetable and arable crop residues"	Presentation	Supply	GreenProtein	http://greenproteinproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/Circular-Bioeconomy-Aarhus-June-2019-Public.pdf
EN	Assessment of potential improvements in efficiency and sustainability of biomass supply chains	Project deliverable	Multiplier	ICT-BIOCHAIN	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/D1.4_-ICT-BIOCHAIN.pdf
EN	Assessment of the current ICT, IoT, and Industry 4.0 solutions in European biomass utilization	Project deliverable	Multiplier	ICT-BIOCHAIN	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/D1.1_Assessment_of_the_current_ICT_IoT_and_Industry_4.0_solutions_in_European_biomass_utilization_-_submission_ready.pdf
EN	WEBINAR: Opportunities for ICT in the Biomass sector	Video	Supply	ICT-BIOCHAIN	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=v254PkX-z8
EN	Recommendations for Digital Innovation Hubs mobilisation	Recommendation	Multiplier	ICT-BIOCHAIN	https://www.arqis.com/apps/Cascade/index.html?appid=bc12d10424e348acb0aad80e72387cb7
EN	Tips from the Andalusian DIH	Video	Multiplier	ICT-BIOCHAIN	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IWgBzFvSTDY
EN	Tips from the Irish DIH	Video	Multiplier	ICT-BIOCHAIN	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FSTpeZc1iE
NL	HandboekBioBased inkopen	Publication	Demand	InnProBio	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/InnProBio_handbook-NL_download.pdf
EN	Handbook on the public procurement of bio-based products and services	Publication	Demand	InnProBio	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/InnProBio_handbook-EN_download.pdf
DE	Handbuch zur öffentlichen Beschaffung von Bio-basierten Produkten und Dienstleistungen	Publication	Demand	InnProBio	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/InnProBio_handbook-DE_download.pdf
PL	Zamówienia na bioprodukty i biouслуги. Podręcznik	Publication	Demand	InnProBio	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/InnProBio_handbook-PL_download.pdf
EN	Bio-based products database and supporting tools for public procurement	Database or repository	Demand	InnProBio	https://www.biobasedconsultancy.com/
EN	Recommendations to decision makers and standardisation bodies	Recommendation	Multiplier	InnProBio	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/InnProBio_D4.6_Recommendations_final.pdf
NL	Wat zijn biobased producten?	Fact Sheet	Demand	InnProBio	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/InnProBio_Factsheets_NL_combined.pdf
EN	What are bio-based products?	Fact Sheet	Demand	InnProBio	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/InnProBio_Factsheets_combined.pdf
EN	Good practices from our projects and beyond	Database or repository	Multiplier	Interreg Europe	https://www.interregeurope.eu/policylearning/good-practices/
EN	Interreg MED Green Growth community Catalogue of project's actionable knowledge	Database or repository	Multiplier	Interreg MED Green Growth	-
EN	Interreg MED Green Growth community Catalogue of project's results	Database or repository	Multiplier	Interreg MED Green Growth	https://interregmedgreengrowth.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/Catalogue-of-Projects-Results_revised.pdf

EN	Synergies for Green Growth	Publication	Multiplier	Interreg MED Green Growth	https://interregmedgreengrowth.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/White-Paper-5-Synergies-for-Green-Growth.pdf
EN	Interreg MED Green Growth Community: Online Communication Training.	Training material	Multiplier	Interreg MED Green Growth	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lceb2F5lp4&feature=emb_imp_woyt
EN	INTRINSIC Connected Educator Platform	Platform	Demand	Intrinsic	https://www.intrinsic.eu/connected-educator-platform.html
EN	INTRINSIC Entrepreneur Monitoring App	Video	Supply	Intrinsic	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pVBqxs145VQ
EN	Participatory process framework model	project deliverable	Multiplier	ISAAC	http://www.isaac-project.it/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/D3.1-Participatory-process-framework-model.pdf
EN	Guidelines for well-done biogas/biomethane plants	project deliverable	Demand, Supply, Multiplier	ISAAC	http://www.isaac-project.it/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/D4.3-Guidelines-for-well-done-biogas-biomethane-plants_EN.pdf
IT	Linee guida per realizzare impiantiper la produzionedi biogas/biometano "fatti bene"	project deliverable	Demand, Supply, Multiplier	ISAAC	http://www.isaac-project.it/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/D4.3-Guidelines-for-well-done-biogas-biomethane-plants_IT.pdf
EN	Report on the application of the tool	project deliverable	Multiplier	ISAAC	http://www.isaac-project.it/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/D4.4-Report-on-the-application-of-the-tool.pdf
EN	Preliminary report on workshops with farmers	project deliverable	Multiplier	ISAAC	http://www.isaac-project.it/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/D4.6-Preliminary-report-on-workshops-with-farmers-1.pdf
EN	METHODOLOGICAL REPORT ONTHE SOCIO-ECONOMIC ANALYSIS	project deliverable	Multiplier	ISAAC	http://www.isaac-project.it/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/D6.2-Methodological-report-on-the-socio-economic-analysis.pdf
EN	Report on viable funding schemes	project deliverable	Multiplier	ISAAC	http://www.isaac-project.it/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/D6.3-Report-on-viable-funding-schemes.pdf
IT	ISAAC - II Tool	Other	Supply	ISAAC	http://www.isaac-project.it/ii-tool/
GR	Περιοχές αποκλεισμού για την εγκατάσταση μονάδων βιοαερίου στη Βόρεια Ελλάδα	Platform	Supply	Isabel	https://isabel-project.eu/el/map/
GR	Rough estimation of a biogas plant viability (in Greek)	Platform	Supply	Isabel	https://isabel-project.eu/tool/
EN	Energy as a Common Good	Video	Multiplier	Isabel	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zuvF0iMafQg
EN	How big is the bioeconomy? Reflections from aneconomic perspective	Publication	Multiplier	JRC	https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/d746df29-8508-11ea-bf12-01aa75ed71a1/language-en
EN	Alternative global transition pathways to 2050: Prospects for the bioeconomy	Publication	Multiplier	JRC	https://publications.irc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC118064
EN	Scientific tools & databases	Database or repository	Multiplier	JRC	https://ec.europa.eu/irc/en/scientific-tools
EN	JRC Digital Media Hub	Database or repository	Multiplier	JRC	https://visitors-centre.irc.ec.europa.eu/en/media
EN	JRC Publications	Database or repository	Multiplier	JRC	https://ec.europa.eu/irc/en/publications-list
EN	Public report on horizontal standard for bio-based carboncontentdetermination	project deliverable	Multiplier	KBBPPS	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Public-report-on-horizontal-standard-for-bio-based-carbon-content-determination.pdf
EN	Biodegradability standards assessment report	project deliverable	Multiplier	KBBPPS	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Biodegradability-standards-assessment-report.pdf
EN	Eco-toxicological impact study	project deliverable	Multiplier	KBBPPS	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/D6.3-Eco-toxicological-impact-study.pdf
EN	Green label report	project deliverable	Multiplier	KBBPPS	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/Green-label-report.pdf
EN	Market entry barriers	project deliverable	Multiplier	KBBPPS	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/Market-entry-barriers.pdf
EN	Key steps to establishing a Digital Innovation Hub	Other	Supply	Key steps to establishing a Digital Innovation Hub	https://www.arcqis.com/apps/Cascade/index.html?appid=ae5361845da94ef08ab0dbc45a26d6cf

EN	Future transitions for the Bioeconomy towards Sustainable Development and a Climate-Neutral Economy Knowledge Synthesis Final Report	Publication	Multiplier	Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy	https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC121212
EN	KnowledgeBase	Database or repository	Multiplier	Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy	https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/bioeconomy_en
EN	Brief on the role of the forest-based bioeconomy in mitigating climate change through carbon storage and material substitution	Publication	Multiplier	Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy	https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC124374
EN	Brief on jobs and growth of the EU bioeconomy 2008-2017	Publication	Multiplier	Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy	https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/publication/brief-jobs-and-growth-eu-bioeconomy-2008-2017
EN	Bioeconomy employment and value added: 2017 data - Infographic	Infographics	Multiplier	Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy	https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/publication/bioeconomy-employment-value-added-2017-data-infographic_en
EN	Brief on biomass production of fisheries and aquaculture	Publication	Multiplier	Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy	https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/publication/brief-biomass-production-fisheries-and-aquaculture
EN	Brief on food waste in the European Union	Publication	Multiplier	Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy	https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/publication/brief-food-waste-european-union
EN	Brief on algae biomass production	Publication	Multiplier	Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy	https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC118214
EN	Bioeconomy Glossary	Other	Multiplier	Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy	https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/bioeconomy/glossary_en
EN	Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy - video on algae biomass production	Video	Multiplier	Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy	https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/publication/knowledge-centre-bioeconomy-video-algae-biomass-production_en
EN	Brief on the use of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) to evaluate environmental impacts of the bioeconomy	Publication	Multiplier	Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy	https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC109817
EN	Brief on biomass for energy in the European Union	Publication	Multiplier	Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy	https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC109354
EN	Brief on forestry biomass production	Publication	Multiplier	Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy	https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC109352
EN	Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy - video on forestry biomass production	Video	Multiplier	Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy	https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/publication/knowledge-centre-bioeconomy-video-forestry-biomass-production_en
EN	Brief on agricultural biomass production	Publication	Multiplier	Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy	https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC109294
EN	Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy - video on agricultural biomass production	Video	Multiplier	Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy	https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/publication/knowledge-centre-bioeconomy-video-agricultural-biomass-production_en
EN	Agorà Social Hub	Platform	Multiplier	LEAP4FNSSA	https://www.leap4fnssa.eu/agora/
EN	FNSSA project database	Database or repository	Multiplier	LEAP4FNSSA	https://library.wur.nl/WebQuery/leap4fnssa-projects?record-status=complete
EN	Lifecab Report for Policy Makers	project deliverable	Multiplier	Lifecab	https://www.lifecab.eu/resources/posts/4/Annex%2017_DD1-6_Report%20of%20LIFECAB%20for%20policymaker.pdf
EN	LIFT Fact Sheet "Awareness raising"	Fact Sheet	Multiplier	LIFT	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/awareness-raising/
EN	European Bioeconomy Library	Database or repository	Multiplier	LIFT	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/
EN	LIFT Fact Sheet "New value chains and business models"	Fact Sheet	Multiplier	LIFT	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/new-value-chains-and-business-models/
EN	LIFT Fact Sheet "Stakeholders engagement and co-creation"	Fact Sheet	Multiplier	LIFT	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/stakeholders-engagement-and-co-creation/
EN	Biomass Availability, Quality, Supply and Sustainability	Fact sheet	Multiplier	LIFT	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/08_LIFT_Factsheets_Biomass_Availability.pdf
EN	Foresight, Market Studies and Market Roadmaps	Fact sheet	Multiplier	LIFT	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/07_LIFT_FactSheets_Foresight.pdf

EN	Industrial Roadmapping	Fact sheet	Multiplier	LIFT	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/11_LIFT_FactSheets_Industrial_Roadmapping.pdf
EN	Open Innovation Platforms and Facilities	Fact sheet	Multiplier	LIFT	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/10_LIFT_FactSheets_Open_Innovation.pdf
EN	Regional Potential, Bioeconomy Strategies and Action Plans	Fact sheet	Multiplier	LIFT	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/05_LIFT_FactSheets_regional_potential.pdf
EN	Standardisation, LCA, Labelling and Regulatory Hurdles	Fact sheet	Multiplier	LIFT	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/04_LIFT_FactSheet_Standardisation_LCA_Labelling_Regulatory_Hurdles.pdf
EN	Uptake of RTD Results	Fact sheet	Multiplier	LIFT	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/06_LIFT_FactSheets_Uptake_RTd.pdf
EN	LIFT Fact Sheet "Bioeconomy Education"	Fact Sheet	Multiplier	LIFT	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/bioeconomy-education/
EN	Magic-Good Practices	Good practice	Supply	Magic	https://zenodo.org/record/3540468#.XcvYYi2X_OQ
EN	Handbook with fact sheets of the existing resource-efficient industrial crops	Project deliverable	Supply	Magic	https://zenodo.org/record/3539166#.XvRjP1XZTY
EN	Bioenergy cropping systems of tomorrow	Presentation	Multiplier	Magic	https://zenodo.org/record/3935582#.X2B-3C1XbOQ
IT	Raccolta della canapa da fibra – Esperienze in Emilia Romagna con prototipo Billeter	Article	Multiplier	Magic	https://zenodo.org/record/4030422#.X2CO9S1XZTY
EN	Skills Gap and Training Needs Analysis	Project deliverable	Multiplier	MPowerBio	https://mpowerbio.eu/sites/default/files/inline-files/MPowerBio%20D1.2_compressed.pdf
EN	Educational Approaches	Project deliverable	Multiplier	NextFOOD	https://www.nextfood-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/m1g9ckuqygsrdz8iu8.pdf
EN	A toolbox for teaching practitioners	Project deliverable	Multiplier	NextFOOD	https://www.nextfood-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/d3.2-nextfood-toolbox-2020-06-30.pdf
EN	Report on educational strategy, year 2	Project deliverable	Multiplier	NextFOOD	https://www.nextfood-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/mfzrauilbsob0zd32ln.pdf
EN	Report on Diagnostics of existing policies	Project deliverable	Multiplier	NextFOOD	https://www.nextfood-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/lw3mnxswz-uk0umqgrm.pdf
EN	Review of existing standards and criteria for evaluation of action learning education and applied research	Project deliverable	Multiplier	NextFOOD	https://www.nextfood-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/lw3mit6z9hxavd2p60x.pdf
EN	NextFood Sustainability Impact Framework	Project deliverable	Multiplier	NextFOOD	https://www.nextfood-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/lw3n-ku0px678bpbshlm.pdf
EN	Inventory of skills and competencies	Project deliverable	Multiplier	NextFOOD	https://www.nextfood-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/lw3lbw_vftdak8vyvxiq.pdf
EN	Audit Tool for Education and Research	Project deliverable	Multiplier	NextFOOD	https://www.nextfood-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/d1.2-audit-tool-for-education-and-research1.pdf
EN	Annual case development report (year 2)	Project deliverable	Multiplier	NextFOOD	https://www.nextfood-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/d2.6-case-development-report-year-2.pdf
EN	NextFOOD Platform	Platform	Multiplier	NextFOOD	https://www.nextfood-project.eu/nextfood-platform/
EN	Agroecology: Action Learning in Farming and Food Systems	Case study	Multiplier	NextFOOD	https://www.nextfood-project.eu/case-1-agroecology-action-learning-in-farming-and-food-systems/
EN	Students and farmers taking food innovations from idea to market	Case study	Multiplier	NextFOOD	https://www.nextfood-project.eu/case-2-students-and-farmers-taking-food-innovations-from-idea-to-market/
EN	Supply chain innovation competition	Case study	Multiplier	NextFOOD	https://www.nextfood-project.eu/case-4-supply-chain-innovation-competition/
EN	Action learning Agriscapes	Case study	Multiplier	NextFOOD	https://www.nextfood-project.eu/case-5-action-learning-agriscapes/
EN	Towards a profitable and sustainable forestry chain	Case study	Multiplier	NextFOOD	https://www.nextfood-project.eu/case-6-towards-a-profitable-and-sustainable-forestry-chain/
EN	Agroecology and sustainable farming systems	Case study	Multiplier	NextFOOD	https://www.nextfood-project.eu/case-7-agroecology-and-sustainable-farming-systems/

EN	Experiential and action learning in sustainable gastronomy (IT)	Case study	Multiplier	NextFOOD	https://www.nextfood-project.eu/case-8-experiential-and-action-learning-in-sustainable-gastronomy-it/
EN	Community of Practice (CoP) for Sustainable innovation in the agrifood systems	Case study	Multiplier	NextFOOD	https://www.nextfood-project.eu/case-11-community-of-practice-cop-for-sustainable-innovation-in-the-agrifood-systems/
EN	Learning from Farmers Training Centres: Multi stakeholder action learning Platform	Case study	Multiplier	NextFOOD	https://www.nextfood-project.eu/case-3-learning-from-farmers-training-centres-multi-stakeholder-action-learning-platform/
EN	Improving sustainability in farming and food systems by bringing in agroecological approach through action learning	Case study	Multiplier	NextFOOD	https://www.nextfood-project.eu/case-9-improving-sustainability-in-farming-and-food-systems-by-bringing-in-agroecological-approach-through-action-learning/
EN	Educating the next generation of professionals in the agrifood system	Case study	Multiplier	NextFOOD	https://www.nextfood-project.eu/case-10-educating-the-next-generation-of-professionals-in-the-agrifood-system/
EN	Improving sustainability in farming and food systems	Case study	Multiplier	NextFOOD	https://www.nextfood-project.eu/case-12-improving-sustainability-in-farming-and-food-systems/
EN	A methodology for the indirect assessment of the renewability of bio-based products	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Open-Bio	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/A-methodology-for-the-indirect-assessment-of-the-renewability-of-bio-based-products.pdf
EN	Acceptance factors for bio-based products and related information systems	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Open-Bio	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/Acceptance-factors-for-bio-based-products-and-related-information-systems.pdf
EN	Direct bio-content automation	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Open-Bio	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/Assessment-and-development-of-automation-of-direct-bio-content.pdf
EN	Bio-based sustainability schemes	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Open-Bio	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/Bio-based-sustainability-schemes.pdf
EN	Definitions for renewable elements and renewable molecules	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Open-Bio	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/Definitions-for-renewable-elements-and-renewable-molecules.pdf
EN	EU bio-based label description and strategy	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Open-Bio	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/Open-Bio_D7-5_summary.pdf
EN	Evaluation of applicable techniques for the determination of the bio-based content	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Open-Bio	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/Evaluation-of-techniques.pdf
EN	Product information list guidelines	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Open-Bio	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/D8.4-Product-information-list-guidelines.pdf
EN	The EU Ecolabel and bio-based products - Learnings from the Open-Bio project	Publication	Multiplier	Open-Bio	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/ECOLABEL_compressed.pdf
EN	Pilots4U Database of bioeconomy open access pilot and multipurpose demo facilities	Database or repository	Supply	Pilots4U	https://biopilots4u.eu/database
EN	Pilots4U Policy Recommendations	Recommendation	Multiplier	Pilots4U	https://biopilots4u.eu/system/files/2019-10/Pilots4U_Document_2019-10-24_2038.pdf
EN	What does industry want from open access facilities?	Other	Multiplier	Pilots4U	https://biopilots4u.eu/system/files/2019-10/Pilots4U_Document_2019-10-24_2075.pdf
EN	Business cases for further investment	Case study	Multiplier	Pilots4U	https://biopilots4u.eu/system/files/2019-10/Pilots4U_Document_2019-10-24_2035.pdf
EN	Policy factsheet 42: Regulation of the use of residual biomass from olive oil industries	Fact sheet	Multiplier	POWER4BIO	https://power4bio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/Policy_factsheet_42.docx
EN	POWER4BIO Business Modelling Methodology	Project deliverable	Multiplier	POWER4BIO	https://power4bio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/POWER4BIO_Business_Modelling_Methodology_CANVAS.docx
EN	Loans for rural development 2014-2020, Estonia	Case study	Multiplier	POWER4BIO	https://power4bio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/case-study_Estonia.pdf
EN	Financial instruments for rural development 2014-2020 Occitanie/Pyrénées-Méditerranée, France	Case study	Multiplier	POWER4BIO	https://power4bio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/case_study_EAFRD_Occitanie.pdf
EN	Catalogue of bioeconomy solutions - Finding key information of promising bioeconomy solutions	Database or repository	Multiplier	POWER4BIO	https://www.bio-based-solutions.eu/#/
EN	Best practice examples	Good practice	Multiplier	POWER4BIO	https://power4bio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/POWER4BIO_D3.4_Best_practices_of_bio-based_solutions.pdf
EN	Bioeconomy Strategy Accelerator Toolkit	Platform	Multiplier	POWER4BIO	http://bioeconomy-strategy-toolkit.eu/
EN	GIS-Tool	Platform	Multiplier	POWER4BIO	https://gis.power4bio.eu/

EN	Key performance indicators to evaluate re-regional bioeconomies	Project deliverable	Multiplier	POWER4BIO	https://power4bio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/POWER4BIO_D2.2_Key-performance-indicators-to-evaluate-regional-bioeconomies_FV.pdf
EN	Recommendations for the use of existing tools when developing regional bioeconomy strategies	Recommendation	Multiplier	POWER4BIO	https://power4bio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/POWER4BIO_D2.3_Tool_inventory_190531_FV.pdf
EN	Catalogue with bio-based solutions	Project deliverable	Supply, Multiplier	POWER4BIO	https://power4bio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/POWER4BIO_D3.3_Catalogue_with_bio-based_solutions.pdf
EN	An overview of suitable regional policies to support bio-based business models	Project deliverable	Multiplier	POWER4BIO	https://power4bio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/POWER4BIO_D4.2_Policies_support_bio-based_business_models_FINAL_doi.pdf
EN	Training design and materials for increasing the bioeconomy capacity of regional stakeholders	Project deliverable	Multiplier	POWER4BIO	https://power4bio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/POWER4BIO_D6.4_Training_design_and_materials_UPDATE2.pdf
EN	New Forms of Land Grabbing Due to the Bioeconomy: The Case of Brazil	Publication	Multiplier	POWER4BIO	https://power4bio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/sustainability-12-03395_Cudlinova.pdf
EN	Report on Policy Lessons	project deliverable	Multiplier	ProBIO	https://www.ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=08016665b628a26a&appId=PPGMS
EN	HELPING BIOECONOMY RESEARCH PROJECTS RAISE THEIR GAME An early glimpse into the lessons learnt from ProBIO	Publication	Multiplier	ProBIO	http://www.probio-project.eu/pdf/ProBIO_brochure_web.pdf
EN	Business stories	Presentation	Supply	ProBIO	http://www.probio-project.eu/pageflow.html
EN	Regional Bioeconomy Profiles	Project deliverable	Multiplier	RD12CluB	https://www.jamk.fi/globalassets/tutkimus-ja-kehitys--research-and-development/tki-projektien-lohkot-ja-tiedostot/rdi2club/materials/rdi2club_regionalbioeconomyprofiles_2.1report_final.pdf
EN	Joint Action Plan of the RD12CluB project partnership for the Development of Knowledge-Driven Regional Bioeconomy Innovation Ecosystems	Project deliverable	Multiplier	RD12CluB	https://www.jamk.fi/globalassets/tutkimus-ja-kehitys--research-and-development/tki-projektien-lohkot-ja-tiedostot/rdi2club/results/rdi2club_jap_2020_updated_26_05_2020.pdf
EN	RD12CluB-project Bioeconomy Action Plan for Central Finland	project deliverable	Multiplier	RD12CluB	https://www.jamk.fi/globalassets/tutkimus-ja-kehitys--research-and-development/tki-projektien-lohkot-ja-tiedostot/rdi2club/results/central-finland-jap_2020version.pdf
EN	Action Plan of the Świętokrzyskie Voivodeship for development of the bioeconomy innovation ecosystem	project deliverable	Multiplier	RD12CluB	https://www.jamk.fi/globalassets/tutkimus-ja-kehitys--research-and-development/tki-projektien-lohkot-ja-tiedostot/rdi2club/results/regap_witokrzyskie_woiwodeship_poland_2019.pdf
EN	Action Plan for Development of a Knowledge-Driven Bioeconomy Innovation Ecosystem in Vidzeme Region in Latvia	project deliverable	Multiplier	RD12CluB	https://www.jamk.fi/globalassets/tutkimus-ja-kehitys--research-and-development/tki-projektien-lohkot-ja-tiedostot/rdi2club/results/regap_vidzeme_region_latvia_2019.pdf
EN	Joint Action Plan for Developing Bio-economy Clusters/Innovation Ecosystems for a Sustainable Bioeconomy in Estonia	project deliverable	Multiplier	RD12CluB	https://www.jamk.fi/globalassets/tutkimus-ja-kehitys--research-and-development/tki-projektien-lohkot-ja-tiedostot/rdi2club/results/regap_estonia_2019.pdf
EN	The Bioeconomy Strategy for the Inland Region 2017-2024A business strategy and action plan	project deliverable	Multiplier	RD12CluB	https://www.jamk.fi/globalassets/tutkimus-ja-kehitys--research-and-development/tki-projektien-lohkot-ja-tiedostot/rdi2club/results/bioekonomistategi-for-inlandet_engelsk-version_oppdatersept19_web.pdf
EN	Biobord platform	Platform	Multiplier	RD12CluB	https://biobord.eu/
EN	25 Cases for Bioeconomy Innovation around the Baltic Sea Region	Case study	Multiplier	RD12CluB	https://www.jamk.fi/globalassets/tutkimus-ja-kehitys--research-and-development/tki-projektien-lohkot-ja-tiedostot/rdi2club/results/25casesforbioeconomy-eng-26082020-web.pdf
CN-DE-EN-ES-FR-HU-IT-NL-SV-SL	Quiz: Food Waste Valorisation	Games	Demand	Refresh	https://eu-refresh.org/quiz/
EN	FoodWaste Explorer	Database or repository	Supply	Refresh	https://foodwasteexplorer.eu/

EN	Policy recommendations to improve food waste prevention and valorisation in the EU	Recommendation	Multiplier	Refresh	https://eu-refresh.org/sites/default/files/D6.5%20Policy%20recommendations_v.2.pdf
EN	A roadmap to reduce food waste in Europe	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Refresh	https://eu-refresh.org/sites/default/files/REFRESH%20D4.8_Road%20Map.pdf
EN	A pan-European simulation of selected interventions	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Refresh	https://eu-refresh.org/sites/default/files/REFRESH%20D4.7_Pan%20European%20Simulations%20of%20selected%20interventions.pdf
EN	Pan-European scenarios of food waste levels	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Refresh	https://eu-refresh.org/sites/default/files/REFRESH_D4.6_Pan%20European%20Scenarios.pdf
EN	Role of food waste valorisation potential - Assessment of the role of waste valorisation in meeting potential targets for waste reduction	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Refresh	https://eu-refresh.org/sites/default/files/D6.13%20valorisation%20contribution%20to%20waste%20targets%20FINAL_06.04.20%20%281%29.pdf
EN	Scale up models and processes	Case study	Supply	Refresh	https://eu-refresh.org/sites/default/files/D6_5_Scale_up_models_and_processes%20Final.pdf
EN	Identification of food waste conversion barriers - Identification of social, economic, legislative and environmental barriers and opportunities	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Refresh	https://eu-refresh.org/sites/default/files/D6.11%20Identification%20of%20food%20waste%20conversion%20barriers_Final.pdf
EN	Avoiding food waste through feeding surplus food to omnivorous non-ruminant livestock	Policy brief	Multiplier	Refresh	https://eu-refresh.org/sites/default/files/REFRESH%20WP3%20Policy%20Brief%20animal%20feed%20final.pdf
EN	REFRESH Policy Brief: Reducing consumer food waste	Policy brief	Multiplier	Refresh	https://eu-refresh.org/sites/default/files/REFRESH_policy_brief_consumer%20food%20waste%20190311.pdf
EN	Regulating the role of Unfair Trading Practices in food waste generation	Policy brief	Multiplier	Refresh	https://eu-refresh.org/sites/default/files/REFRESH%20Policy%20Brief%20on%20UTPs_2019_FINAL.pdf
EN	Voluntary Agreements as a collaborative solution for food waste reduction	Policy brief	Multiplier	Refresh	https://eu-refresh.org/sites/default/files/REFRESH%20Policy%20Brief%20on%20VAs_2019_FINAL.pdf
EN	New leaflet for explaining benefits of intercropping Crop Mixtures: a way to reduce herbicides. ReMIX Wheat Lentil Trial	Infographics	Supply	ReMIX	https://www.remix-intercrops.eu/content/download/4157/39467/version/1/file/NLMAP_leaflet.lnk.pdf
EN	Mixed cultures peas/barley - Does it need its own breeding? (in German)	Video	Supply	ReMIX	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Vdz7bixA_Pc
DE	Mixed cultures peas/barley - Does it need its own breeding? (in German)	Video	Supply	ReMIX	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Fvu-LN2d4Jo
EN	Intercropping Redesigning cropping strategies for food production and environmental services	Policy brief	Multiplier	ReMIX	https://www.remix-intercrops.eu/content/download/4186/39689/version/1/file/ReMIX_Policy%20Brief%201.pdf
EN	Intercropping for boosting organic farming in Europe	Policy brief	Multiplier	ReMIX	https://www.remix-intercrops.eu/content/download/4187/39692/version/1/file/ReMIX_Policy%20Brief%202.pdf
EN	Contribution of intercropping to pesticide use reduction	Policy brief	Multiplier	ReMIX	https://www.remix-intercrops.eu/content/download/4188/39695/version/1/file/ReMIX_Policy%20Brief%203.pdf
EN	Improved support for intercropping will reduce fertiliser inputs and nutrient losses	Policy brief	Multiplier	ReMIX	https://www.remix-intercrops.eu/content/download/4189/39698/version/1/file/ReMIX_Policy%20Brief%204.pdf
EN	Harvesting and separating crop mixtures: yes we can!	Policy brief	Multiplier	ReMIX	https://www.remix-intercrops.eu/content/download/4190/39701/version/1/file/ReMIX_Policy%20Brief%205.pdf
EN	Report on regulatory barriers	Project deliverable	Multiplier	RoadToBio	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/RoadToBio_D21_RegulatoryBarriers.pdf
EN	Public perception of bio-based products	Project deliverable	Multiplier	RoadToBio	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/RoadToBio_D22_Public_perception_of_bio-based_products.pdf
EN	COMMUNICATION GUIDE – HOW TO PROMOTE BIO-BASED PRODUCTS	Fact sheet	Multiplier	RoadToBio	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/RoadToBio_factsheet_2_communication_guide.pdf
EN	KEY MESSAGES FOR COMMUNICATION ABOUT BIO-BASED PRODUCTS	Fact sheet	Multiplier	RoadToBio	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/RoadToBio_factsheet_3_key_messages.pdf

EN	Virtual Library	Database or repository	Supply	Rubizmo	https://rubizmo.eu/business/virtual-library
EN	Transformation Support Tool	Platform	Supply	Rubizmo	https://rubizmo.eu/business/transformation-support-tool
EN	Supporting local bioenergy development	Policy Brief	Multiplier	Rubizmo	https://rubizmo.eu/attachment/render/Baecca55-11f5-471c-86f0-710091df2e77
EN	Handbook for agro-industries interested in starting a new activity as biomass logistic centre: Lessons learned and good practice examples	Good practice	Supply	Rubizmo	https://rubizmo.eu/attachment/render/dfbb206-f1d2-4ff5-a255-cedde7734f21
EN	FARMERS TRAINING ENTREPRENEURSHIP MANUAL	Training Material	Supply	Rubizmo	https://rubizmo.eu/attachment/render/afa93ffd-0f2e-4e93-a2e7-025f089efb88
EN	Cooperation Toolkit	Platform	Supply	Rubizmo	https://rubizmo.eu/cooperation-toolkit
PL	Przewidywane rozwiązania dla nowoczesnych gospodarstw wiejskich	Policy Brief	Multiplier	Rubizmo	https://rubizmo.eu/attachment/render/b1bd80e8-142e-44ab-a36c-5ce846980721
EN	RURAL 3.0. a framework for rural development	Publication	Multiplier	Rubizmo	https://rubizmo.eu/attachment/render/d1e5f527-c2f7-41a3-bad4-092d51dd126c
EN	Anticipated Futures for Modern Rural Economies	Policy Brief	Multiplier	Rubizmo	https://rubizmo.eu/attachment/render/fbb3655-bef5-4ed6-9a49-3db33baa2cf7
EN	Atlas with regional cost supply biomass potentials for EU 28, Western Balkan Countries, Moldavia, Turkey and Ukraine	Project deliverable	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://s2biom.wenr.wur.nl/doc/S2Biom_D1_8_v1_1_FINAL_19_04_2017_CP.pdf
EN	Database of biomass conversion technologies	Project deliverable	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/S2Biom_Database_of_Biomass_Conversion_Technologies.pdf
EN	Integrated assessment of biomass supply chains and conversion routes under different scenarios	Project deliverable	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/D7.3_S2Biom_Integrated_Assessment_Final.pdf
EN	Tools for biomass chains	Platform	Supply	S2Biom	https://s2biom.wenr.wur.nl/web/quest/home
EN	Synergies and cooperation for biobased economy in Europe and at international level	Project deliverable	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://s2biom.wenr.wur.nl/doc/S2Biom_D6.4%20final.pdf
EN	R&D roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass in Europe	Project deliverable	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://s2biom.wenr.wur.nl/doc/S2Biom_D8%204%20Roadmap%20final.pdf
EN	Sustainable supply of non-food biomass for a resource efficient bioeconomy	Project deliverable	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://s2biom.wenr.wur.nl/doc/S2biom_review_state-of_the_art_Final.pdf
EN	Cover report Results logistical case studies	Project deliverable	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://s2biom.wenr.wur.nl/doc/D3.4+D3.6%20-%20Logistical%20case%20studies%20-%20cover%20report%20161216.pdf
EN	Guidelines on assessing bioeconomy value chain sustainability performance	Project deliverable	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/D5.5_S2Biom_Guidelines_on_assessing_sustainability_performance_Final.pdf
EN	Policy database	Database or repository	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/D6.1_S2Biom_Policy_Database_Final.pdf
EN	Policy options to mobilize sustainable non-food biomass resources for the biobased economy Version 2	Project deliverable	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/D6.3_S2Biom_Policy_Options_Final.pdf
EN	Report on benchmarking of country policy approaches Version 2.0	Project deliverable	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/D6.2_S2Biom_Benchmarking_of_Policy_Approaches_Final.pdf
EN	Albania Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-ALBANIA-biomass-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Austria Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-AUSTRIA-biomass-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Belgium Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-BELGIUM-biomass-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Bosnia & Herzegovina Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-BOSNIA--HERZEGOVINA-outlook-potential-and-policies.pdf

EN	Bulgaria Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-BULGARIA-biomass-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Croatia Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-CROATIA-biomass-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Czech Republic Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-CZECH-REPUBLIC-biomass-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Denmark Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-DENMARK-biomass-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Estonia Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-ESTONIA-biomass-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Finland Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-FINLAND-outlook-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	FYR of Macedonia Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-FYROM-biomass-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	France Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-FRANCE-outlook-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Germany Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-GERMANY-biomass-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Greece Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-GREECE-biomass-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Hungary Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-HUNGARY-biomass-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Ireland Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-IRELAND-biomass-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Italy Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-ITALY-biomass-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Kosovo Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-KOSOVO-outlook-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Latvia Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-LATVIA-biomass-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Lithuania Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-LITHUANIA-biomass-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Luxemburg Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-LUXEMBURG-biomass-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Malta Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-MALTA-outlook-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Moldova Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-MOLDOVA-outlook-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Montenegro Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-MONTENEGRO-outlook-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Netherlands Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-NETHERLANDS-biomass-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Poland Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-POLAND-biomass-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Portugal Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-PORTUGAL-outlook-potential-and-policies.pdf

EN	Romania Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-ROMANIA-biomass-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Serbia Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-SERBIA-biomass-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Slovakia Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-SLOVAKIA-biomass-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Slovenia Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-SLOVENIA-biomass-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Spain Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-SPAIN-biomass-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Sweden Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-SWEDEN-biomass-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Turkey Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-TURKEY-biomass-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Ukraine Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-UKRAINE-biomass-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	United Kingdom Roadmap for lignocellulosic biomass and relevant policies for a bio-based economy in 2030	Presentation	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/WP8_Country_Outlook/Final_Roadmaps_March/S2Biom-UNITED-KINGDOM-biomass-potential-and-policies.pdf
EN	Assessment of biomass production potential from short rotation crops (SRC) on unused agricultural land for use in biomass power plants in Croatia	Case study	Supply	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/S2biom---T932---SCS-Croatia---report.pdf
EN	Case study on supplying large scale Biofuel production plants in North-East Germany and North West Poland with lignocellulosic feedstock from the region	Case study	Supply	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/S2biom---T932---SCS-Germany-Poland---report.pdf
EN	Methodology for measuring the economic development of biomass value chains, in West Region, Romania	Case study	Supply	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/S2biom---T932---SCS-Romania---report.pdf
EN	PLANT FOR LIGNOCELLULOSIC BIOETHANOL PRODUCTION IN SERBIA Case Study	Case study	Supply	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/S2biom---T932---SCS-Serbia---report.pdf
EN	Biomass co-firing in lignite-fired power plants as a means of mobilizing agro-biomass resources	Case study	Supply	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/S2Biom_D9.6_Case_Study_Biomass_cofiring_in_lignite_plants.pdf
EN	Policy Brief: New supply & demand data on biomass use for energy, fuels & organic chemicals in Europe	Policy brief	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/D10.17a_S2Biom_Policy_brief_Improved_dataets_for_the_bio-based_economy_Final.pdf
EN	Policy Brief: Vision for 1 billion tonnes of dry lignocellulosic biomass for the biobased economy in 2030	Policy brief	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/D10.17b_S2Biom_Policy_brief_Vision_to_2030_Final.pdf
EN	Policy Brief: Long term strategies for lignocellulosic biomass in Europe	Policy brief	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/D10.17c_S2Biom_Policy_brief_Long_term_strategies_for_lignocellulosic_biomass_Final.pdf
EN	Policy Brief: Market analysis for biobased products	Policy brief	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/D10.17d_S2Biom_Policy_brief_Market_analysis_for_biobased_products_Final.pdf
EN	Policy Brief: Biomass Potentials in the S2Biom project	Policy brief	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/D10.17e_S2Biom_Policy_brief_Definition_of_biomass_potentials_in_S2Biom_Final.pdf
EN	Roadmap for regional end-users on how to collect, process, store and maintain biomass supply data	Project deliverable	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/D1.1_S2Biom_Roadmap_on_biomass_data_Final.pdf
EN	TOWARDS SUSTAINABILITY	Publication	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/01_Biobased_001-017.pdf
EN	Sustainability Scenarios for a Resource Efficient Europe	Project progress/final report	Multiplier	S2Biom	https://www.s2biom.eu/images/Publications/SustScen_Report_Final_Cambridge_econometrics_resource_efficient_europe.pdf

EN	Overview of the Systems Analysis Framework for the EU Bioeconomy	Project deliverable	Multiplier	SAT-BBE	https://www.wecr.wur.nl/Bers/Publications/SAT-BBE%20-%20WP1%20-%20Deliverable%201%204_%20Final%20131118.pdf
EN	Design of asystems analysis tools framework for a EU bioeconomy strategy	project deliverable	Multiplier	SAT-BBE	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/SAT-BBE-Final-Report-D3.3.pdf
EN	Operational relationship between analytical tools available in the framework	project deliverable	Multiplier	SAT-BBE	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/SAT-BBE-Deliverable-3.1-final-30-Nov2014.pdf
EN	Toolkit for a Systems Analysis Framework of the EU Bioeconomy	project deliverable	Multiplier	SAT-BBE	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/SAT-BBE-Deliverable-2-4-Sept14.pdf
EN	Multi-level stakeholder engagement analysis, including gender, and impact analysis	Project deliverable	Multiplier	SCALIBUR	http://multisite.iris.cat/scalibur/files/2021/05/Attachment_0-1.pdf
EN	Stakeholder engagement plan per pilot municipality and identification of current promising practices	Project deliverable	Multiplier	SCALIBUR	http://www.scalibur.eu/files/2020/07/Attachment_0-1.pdf
EN	Biowaste collection strategies	Presentation	Multiplier	SCALIBUR	http://multisite.iris.cat/scalibur/files/2021/05/ITENE_Webinar-1_2021_05_05.pdf
EN	Engaging and Encouraging Stakeholders To Think Green Everyday	Presentation	Multiplier	SCALIBUR	http://www.scalibur.eu/files/2019/06/Rosa-Strube-CSCP-Engaging-and-Encouraging-Stakeholders-To-Think-Green-Everyday.pdf
EN	SHERPA Publications	Database or repository	Multiplier	SHERPA	https://rural-interfaces.eu/publications/
EN	SHERPA Position Paper RURAL POLICIES TO PROTECT AND ENHANCE BIODIVERSITY THROUGH LANDSCAPE FEATURES	Publication	Multiplier	SHERPA	https://rural-interfaces.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/SHERPA_PositionPaper-Biodiversity.pdf
EN	SHERPA Position Paper LONG-TERM VISION FOR RURAL AREAS	Publication	Multiplier	SHERPA	https://rural-interfaces.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/SHERPA_PositionPaper-LTVRA.pdf
EN	Timeline for EU programming	Platform	Multiplier	SHERPA	https://rural-interfaces.eu/resources-and-tools/timeline-for-eu-programming/
EN	STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT TOOL - HOW TO MAKE ONLINE CALLS OR VIDEOCALLS?	Fact sheet	Multiplier	SHERPA	https://rural-interfaces.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/SHERPA_OSES_Guidance-sheet_8.pdf
EN	STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT TOOL - HOW TO SET UP A CONSULTATION WITH STAKEHOLDERS?	Fact sheet	Multiplier	SHERPA	https://rural-interfaces.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/SHERPA_OSES_Guidance-sheet_9.pdf
EN	STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT TOOL - HOW TO SHARE ONLINE FILES AND DOCUMENTS?	Fact sheet	Multiplier	SHERPA	https://rural-interfaces.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/SHERPA_OSES_Guidance-sheet_11.pdf
EN	STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT TOOL - HOW TO ANALYSE STAKEHOLDERS IN VIEW OF ACHIEVING AND MAINTAINING THEIR ENGAGEMENT IN A MAP?	Fact sheet	Multiplier	SHERPA	https://rural-interfaces.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/SHERPA_OSES_Guidance-sheet_12.pdf
EN	STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT TOOL - HOW TO MONITOR AND ASSESS THE LEVEL OF ENGAGEMENT OF STAKEHOLDERS IN MAPS' ACTIVITIES?	Fact sheet	Multiplier	SHERPA	https://rural-interfaces.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/SHERPA_OSES_Guidance-sheet_14.pdf
EN	STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT TOOL - HOW TO ORGANISE A MAPEVENT AT REGIONAL AND LOCAL LEVEL?	Fact sheet	Multiplier	SHERPA	https://rural-interfaces.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/SHERPA_OSES_Guidance-sheet_1.pdf
EN	SMARTCHAIN INNOVATION PLATFORM	Platform	Demand, Supply, Multiplier	Smartchain	https://www.smartchain-platform.eu/
EN	SmartPilots Factsheets and Customer Survey Financial Instruments for Shared Pilots Facilities (SPF) in the Bioeconomy	project deliverable	Multiplier	SmartPilots	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/Report-on-SmartPilots-Factsheets-and-Survey_Final_14May2018.pdf
EN	SmartPilots Policy Recommendations 20190430	Video	Multiplier	SmartPilots	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PMR6HG_MEi8
EN	Report on end-of-lifesocial and socio-economic assessment	Project deliverable	Multiplier	STAR-PROBIO	http://www.star-probio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/D6.4-Final.pdf
EN	Mapping of Relevant Value chains and stakeholders	Project deliverable	Multiplier	STAR-PROBIO	http://www.star-probio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/D1.2_Final-V1.0.pdf

EN	Selection of environmental indicators and impact categories for the life cycle assessment of bio-based products	Project deliverable	Multiplier	STAR-PROBIO	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/STAR-ProBio_D2.2_v1.2.pdf
EN	Assessing Sustainability of Managed End-of-life Options for Bio-based Products in a Circular Economy	Project deliverable	Multiplier	STAR-PROBIO	http://www.star-probio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/D3.2_Star-ProBio_Ver-1.4.pdf http://www.star-probio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/STAR-ProBio-Report-5.2_Final_1.0.pdf
EN	Results of the experiment / Case study	Case Study	Multiplier	STAR-PROBIO	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/STAR-ProBio_D7.1_Final_2.pdf
EN	Examination of existing ILUC approaches and their application to bio-based materials	Project deliverable	Multiplier	STAR-PROBIO	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/STAR-ProBio_D7.1_Final_2.pdf
EN	Recommendations for Standards and criteria for eco-labels for bio-based products	Recommendation	Multiplier	STAR-PROBIO	http://www.star-probio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/STAR-ProBio_D9.2_final.pdf
EN	Acceptance factors among consumers and businesses for bio-based sustainability schemes	Project deliverable	Multiplier	STAR-PROBIO	http://www.star-probio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/STAR-ProBio_D5.1_final.pdf
EN	Criteria and indicators developed for conducting S-LCA social impact assessment	Project deliverable	Multiplier	STAR-PROBIO	http://www.star-probio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/STAR-ProBio-D6.3_final.pdf
EN	Land Use Changes applied to case studies	Case Study	Multiplier	STAR-PROBIO	http://www.star-probio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/STAR-ProBio_D7.2_31012020v1.pdf
EN	Set of recommendations for land use policies	Recommendation	Multiplier	STAR-PROBIO	http://www.star-probio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/STAR-ProBio-D7.3_Final.pdf
EN	Recommendations concerning current sustainability standards associated with bio-based products and amendments to current standards of bio-based products	Recommendation	Multiplier	STAR-PROBIO	http://www.star-probio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/D8.1_Recommendations-concerning-current-sustainability-standards-associated-with-bio-based-products-and-amendments-to-current-standards-of-bio-based-products.pdf
EN	Blueprint of sustainability certification schemes for bio-based products	project deliverable	Multiplier	STAR-PROBIO	http://www.star-probio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/D8.2_SAT-ProBio-blueprint_final-report_3-scalone.pdf
EN	Sustainably criteria for the production of bio-based products —Integrated assessment tool	project deliverable	Supply	STAR-PROBIO	http://www.star-probio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/D8.3_Final-Version.pdf
EN	Comprehensive overview of existing regulatory and voluntary frameworks on sustainability assessment	project deliverable	Multiplier	STAR-PROBIO	http://www.star-probio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/STAR-ProBio-D9.1_V-1.0.pdf
EN	Proposal for a co-regulation framework for the use of sustainability certification schemes in the production of bio-based products	project deliverable	Multiplier	STAR-PROBIO	http://www.star-probio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/D9.3_Proposal-for-a-coregulation-framework_Final.pdf
EN	Report on policy effectiveness and alternative scenarios comparison	project deliverable	Multiplier	STAR-PROBIO	http://www.star-probio.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/FINAL_STAR_ProBio_D9.5.pdf
EN	Identification of technological trends in selected value chains	Project deliverable	Multiplier	STAR4BBI	https://www.biobasedeconomy.eu/app/uploads/sites/2/2018/09/Please-click-here-to-access-deliverable-3.1.pdf
EN	Regulatory and Standardization needs in bio-based industries	Project deliverable	Multiplier	STAR4BBI	https://www.biobasedeconomy.eu/app/uploads/sites/2/2018/09/FINAL-D3.2.pdf
EN	Policy paper on strategy for development of an RCS framework	Project deliverable	Multiplier	STAR4BBI	https://www.star4bbi.eu/app/uploads/sites/11/2019/09/D3.3-Sustainability-Certification-for-all-Products_final.pdf
EN	Regulation action plan	Project deliverable	Multiplier	STAR4BBI	https://www.star4bbi.eu/app/uploads/sites/11/2019/09/D4.4_Regulation-action-plan_final.pdf
EN	Market entry barriers report	Project deliverable	Multiplier	STAR4BBI	https://www.biobasedeconomy.eu/app/uploads/sites/2/2018/09/Please-click-here-to-access-deliverable-2.1.pdf
EN	Report on implementation for creation of new or revised standards	Project deliverable	Multiplier	STAR4BBI	https://www.biobasedeconomy.eu/app/uploads/sites/2/2019/05/STAR4BBI_WP4_D4.3_Final-Report.pdf
EN	SuperBIO: Building and supporting new bio-based value chains with SMEs	Project deliverable	Multiplier	SuperBIO	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/SuperBIOguidancedocument.pdf
PT	COMO O PROJETO TRADEIT TEM AJUDADO PMES DO SETOR DA PANIFICAÇÃO	Publication	Multiplier	Tradeit	https://bibliotecadigital.ipb.pt/bitstream/10198/14279/3/Artigo%20AIPAN.pdf

PT	Análise ao processo de fabrico de pão do Nordeste Transmontano com vista à elaboração de um caderno de especificações -Estudo Preliminar	Publication	Multiplier	Tradeit	https://bibliotecadigital.ipb.pt/bitstream/11198/14109/1/Ana%cc%81lise%20ao%20processo%20de%20fabrico%20de%20pa%cc%83a.pdf
EN	Conceptual framework of the awareness, communication and education toolkits – 1st version	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Transition2BIO	https://www.transition2bio.eu/public_result/conceptual-framework-of-the-awareness-communication-and-education-toolkits-1st-version/
EN	First Consolidated Action Plan of Awareness and Communication Activities	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Transition2BIO	https://www.transition2bio.eu/public_result/first-consolidated-action-plan-of-awareness-and-communication-activities/
EN	Artificial Intelligence for fermentative bioprocess control	Case Study	Multiplier	Urbiofuture	https://www.uab.cat/web/news-detail/artificial-intelligence-for-fermentative-bioprocess-control-1345680342044.html?noticiaid=1345822515176
EN	Nanoplastics in biosensors for detecting histamine in wine	Case Study	Multiplier	Urbiofuture	https://www.uab.cat/web/news-detail/nanoplastics-in-biosensors-for-detecting-histamine-in-wine-1345680342044.html?noticiaid=1345825122630
EN	Composting of sewage sludge from urban wastewater treatment plants and the associated gaseous emissions: Characterization of odours and greenhouse gases	Case Study	Multiplier	Urbiofuture	https://www.uab.cat/web/news-detail/composting-of-sewage-sludge-from-urban-wastewater-treatment-plants-and-the-associated-gaseous-emissions-characterization-of-odours-and-greenhouse-gases-1345680342044.html?noticiaid=1345812035902
EN	Educational programmes	Database or repository	Demand	Urbiofuture	https://www.urbiofuture.eu/educational_programmes/
PL	Urbiofuture webinar in Polish language	Video	Multiplier	Urbiofuture	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hU8k6oK9xdQ
EN	Why should you pursue a career in bioeconomy?	Video	Demand	Urbiofuture	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oilSL9-t2cE
ES	¿Por qué estudiar una carrera relacionada con la bioeconomía?	Video	Demand	Urbiofuture	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BluNrpC5VOc
EN	Bio-based stakeholders completed and classified list	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Urbiofuture	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/D2.1-ListStakeholders_WEB.pdf
EN	Results from the dynamic workshop fostering dialogue organization	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Urbiofuture	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/D4.1_dynamic_workshop_v2.pdf
EN	Results from the co-creation exercise	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Urbiofuture	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/D4.2-results_from_the_co-creation_exercise.pdf
EN	Focus Group Report	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Urbiofuture	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/Focus_Group_ReportVF.pdf
EN	Guide of best practices for cooperation between academia and industry based on success cases	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Urbiofuture	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/Guide_of_Best_Practices.pdf
EN	Report about the analysis of educational gaps identified in the different regional contexts and action fields	Project deliverable	Multiplier	Urbiofuture	https://www.bioeconomy-library.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/D3.3_Report_about_the_analysis_of_educational_gaps_identified_pics.pdf
EN	ROOTS -circular Policies for changing the bioWaste System	Project deliverable	Multiplier	ValueWaste	http://valuewaste.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/Position-Paper-Policy-Working-Group_final.pdf
EN	Kalundborg-Symbiosis:Successful case and role in ValueWaste	Case Study	Multiplier	ValueWaste	http://valuewaste.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/D6.1.-Kalundborg-Symbiosis_VALUEWASTE.pdf
EN	Catalogue of urban biowaste solutions and good practices examples	Good practice	Multiplier	Waystap	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1eIlP0XldBwCfL9-1SGak8aPz4TitSa0W/view

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